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Corresponding author

Corresponding author	Remko Detz
Affiliation	TNO
Email address	remko.detz@tno.nl

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Partner	Name
Gasunie, NBNL, TNO	Adriaan de Bakker, Udo Huisman (Gasunie) Bart Vogelzang (NBNL/Alliander) Marcel Weeda (TNO)
NEC	Steef Kalsbeek

Executive summary

The energy transition and the role of hydrogen

To reach the goals of the Paris Agreement, the energy and industrial sector need to transition to a system with zero or low greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. In most outlooks for a future energy system, low-carbon hydrogen plays a key role, both in reducing emissions from existing hydrogen production for industry as well as to fulfil other, novel applications, such as low-emission energy carrier, fuel, and chemical feedstock and as a means to convert and store variable renewable electricity. Multiple routes to produce low-carbon hydrogen can be applied, such as, capture and underground storage of CO₂ emissions from conventional plants, biomass gasification, and water electrolysis. The transition, thus, requires both the repurposing of existing hydrogen systems and the introduction of new systems and technologies.

Spatial area requirements of the hydrogen system

The new hydrogen system will also occupy space and specific choices in the design of such a system may have a substantial impact on the spatial area requirements, which, especially in a densely populated country as the Netherlands, can have consequences for its deployment. The various policy targets, plans, and scenario studies raise the question of what the spatial footprint will be for the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands. This basic question is further explored within this study in which the spatial consequences of the hydrogen system in four different future energy systems from the Integrale Infrastructuurverkenning 2030-3050 (I13050) scenario report are analysed in more detail.

The goal of the analysis presented in this report is threefold:

1. Validate the assumptions for spatial requirements from the I13050 and Programma Energie Hoofdinfrastructuur (PEH) studies
2. Include new and improved spatial requirements for key subsystems of the future hydrogen system
3. Provide a spatial assessment of the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands based on the data of the I13050 scenarios

The study focuses on the assessment of the spatial requirements of the hydrogen system in the Netherlands up to 2050. For each of the I13050 scenarios, an inventory is made of the different identified hydrogen subsystems and their capacities. These subsystems cover hydrogen supply, transport, storage, and use, but, exclude related systems for electricity production from solar and wind power, and the capture, transport and storage of CO₂.

Next, the spatial footprint of each of these hydrogen subsystems is determined, either by validation of the already reported values from the I13050 report, or by consultation of other reports and data sources. In the following step, the capacities of the hydrogen subsystems from the scenario data are multiplied by the specific spatial footprint of these subsystems to quantify the area requirements for each of the scenarios. The results and implications thereof are also presented and discussed before finishing with the main conclusions.

Figure 0.1. Overview of hydrogen system and key subsystems in scope for this study (for enlarged version: see the Appendix)

Hydrogen system in the scenarios

The role of hydrogen in the I13050 scenarios and the Investment Plans (IP2024) scenarios is analysed and several hydrogen subsystems are identified, covering a variety of options to supply, transport, store, and use hydrogen. The capacities of the hydrogen subsystems are determined for several years up to 2050 for each of the scenarios.

Figure 0.2. Hydrogen production and import capacities in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios for 2030, 2040, and 2050

The choices made in the development of the scenarios show that for some of the subsystems the projected capacity may differ an order of magnitude between scenarios. These differences in subsystem capacity already indicate one of the uncertainties in the assessment of the future space requirement of the hydrogen system.

Spatial area use of the hydrogen subsystems

For each of the key hydrogen subsystems, the spatial footprint is analysed based on several sources, such as the plot size of existing facilities or through consultation of reports and other data sources. The findings related to the spatial requirements per subsystem are summarised in the table below. To cover the entire bandwidth and, thus, most variation, the extremes of the ranges have been used for the calculation of the low and high spatial requirements. The only exception to this method are small-scale electrolyzers, of which the specific spatial footprint is excluded in the determination of the full range for onshore electrolysis.

Table 0.1. Overview of subsystems and their spatial footprint

Category	Subsystem ¹	Unit	Spatial footprint ²
Hydrogen production	Onshore large-scale electrolyser	ha/GW _e	10-44
	Onshore small-scale electrolyser	ha/GW _e	4.5-208
	Offshore electrolyser	ha/GW _e	0.6-10
	Steam methane reformer (SMR)	ha/GW _{H2}	5-21
	Autothermal reformer (ATR)	ha/GW _{H2}	14
	Biomass gasification	ha/GW _{H2}	39-332
Hydrogen import	Ammonia import and storage	ha/GW _{H2}	3.1-12
	Ammonia cracker	ha/GW _{H2}	2.8-12
	Liquid hydrogen import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	6.8-40
	Methanol import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	0.9
	Methanol reformer	ha/GW _{H2}	5-21
	LOHC import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	4.1-5.6
	LOHC dehydrogenation	ha/GW _{H2}	Only demo, excl. from analysis
Hydrogen storage	Salt caverns	ha/TWh	10-63
	Depleted gas fields	ha/TWh	1.5-150
Hydrogen demand	Refuelling stations	ha/TWh _{H2} /year	58-108
	Hydrogen CCGT	ha/GW _e	4-26
	Hydrogen GT	ha/GW _e	5-15

¹ Ranges of the subsystems that are represented in bold are used to determine the total area requirements in the spatial analysis. ² For most existing facilities, Google Earth is also used to estimate the spatial footprint. Sources are provided in Table 15.

The bandwidths in the spatial footprint for the different hydrogen subsystems result from both a level of uncertainty in the estimated value and varying plot sizes of different facilities, caused by factors like the scale and safety contours of a subsystem and the land price and availability in the region. The designated spatial area use of a hydrogen subsystem is also influenced by how this area is defined. If only the footprint of the installed equipment is considered, the total area usage is considerably smaller compared to a footprint estimate of an entire facility including auxiliary equipment, buildings, and surrounding area. The total footprint can be even larger when licensed, permitted, or underground area is also incorporated in the spatial area assessment. Most ranges are determined based on area requirements of existing subsystems and therefore include differences caused by location, scale, and safety contours. For underground storage, we included the area ascribed to permits and licences for use of the (under)ground within our range. Underground hydrogen storage in depleted gas fields in the Netherlands would be new and may lead to new perceptions of safety contours, possibly extending the spatial requirements and/or limit multi-use space. Based on these considerations, we believe that most uncertainty is covered by the high end of the described ranges and higher specific area requirements seem unlikely unless, for instance, risk and safety contours apply for specific locations.

Total area requirement of the hydrogen system

The spatial footprints of each of the hydrogen subsystems are combined with the required capacities for these subsystems based on the different scenarios to quantify the total area requirement of the hydrogen system. The total spatial area requirements are estimated at 80-101 km² in 2030, 84-217 km² in 2040, and 99-280 km² in 2050. When the pipeline system is excluded, the spatial area estimates are or 3-24 km² in 2030, 7-92 km² in 2040, and 11-155 km² in 2050. The high estimates are especially significant. For comparison, the land area of the island Texel equals 160 km². It is, however, limited if compared to the area required to harvest energy. In the I13050 study, it is indicated that offshore wind may require 3,800-7,200 km², onshore wind 1,250-2,500 km², and solar parks 350-580 km². Arguably, a substantial share of these areas can be ascribed to the hydrogen system, for instance to supply electricity for electrolysis. These systems are, however, excluded from our scope. The International Trade scenario requires the most space for both the low and high estimates, while the space requirements for the other scenarios are lower and the differences between these are limited.

Figure 0.3. Bandwidth estimates of the total spatial requirement for the hydrogen subsystems included in the analysis

The low and high estimates for each scenario result from the bandwidths in spatial footprint, which is described for (nearly) all of the subsystems. Only for the pipeline subsystem, an exception is made and no range is described, as we follow the same reasoning as in the I13050 scenarios.

Area requirements of the different hydrogen subsystems

The largest spatial area requirement is for the hydrogen pipeline network, from 77 km² in 2030 up to 88-125 km² in 2050. This indicated area requirement includes new, repurposed, and multi-use space for these pipeline systems. The majority, currently estimated at 67–85%, of the high pressure pipeline network will be repurposed from the natural gas grid. New high pressure pipelines (HTL) are placed in existing pipeline corridors and hence also do not claim new space, if these pipeline corridors will remain. Arguably, the option exists to reduce our dependence on gaseous fuels and feedstocks and

free up space by removing entire pipeline corridors. The regional hydrogen pipelines (RTL) require slightly more specific space than natural gas RTL pipelines due to safety distances, even if they are placed in the same location as the existing natural gas pipelines. Overall, the area required for the hydrogen RTL network is, however, still lower than that of the current natural gas RTL grid. For the distribution networks, no spatial footprint has been estimated due to uncertainty about the length of pipelines required.

Other significant contributors to land area use are underground hydrogen storage in salt caverns and depleted gas fields (0.1–89 km² in 2050), and hydrogen refuelling stations (3–35 km² in 2050). For these categories it can also be expected that existing infrastructure and assets, such as natural gas storage facilities and fuelling tank stations for conventional fuels, can be largely accommodated for the hydrogen system. The broad range observed in area needs for underground hydrogen storage is mainly influenced by either including the total permitted surface area or only the aboveground installations.

Hydrogen import can also occupy substantial amounts of space. The hydrogen import method (e.g., via liquid hydrogen or ammonia), and the required base and peak capacity each have an impact on the total area requirements, which ranges from 2 to 21 km² in 2050.

Hydrogen production through methane reforming and water electrolysis requires modest amounts of land area, 0.1–2 km² and 1–13 km² in 2050 for methane reforming and total electrolysis, respectively. If more electrolyser capacity can be installed offshore, the spatial requirements on land can decrease. The specific spatial footprint of biomass gasification is relatively high (0.1–2.8 km² in 2050) and if more hydrogen is produced via this route, the area requirements increase substantially. Electricity production by hydrogen gas turbines may play a role in the future energy system, and area requirements for this application vary between 0.5 and 3.6 km² in 2050. This range is largely determined by the bandwidth of the specific spatial footprint for hydrogen-fired gas turbines.

The IJ3050 scenarios also made spatial footprint estimates for the HTL and RTL pipeline networks, electrolysers, hydrogen storage, and hydrogen gas turbines. The PEH study also includes a spatial estimate for gas import terminals, but it is not clear whether this refers to LNG or also to hydrogen. The spatial area estimates in our study align well with the estimates in the IJ3050 and PEH studies in terms of order of magnitude, but the IJ3050 and PEH estimates tend to be on the lower side of our determined bandwidths.

Hydrogen system in perspective

The projected spatial area requirement of the hydrogen system, based on the IJ3050 scenarios, is also compared to other systems in the Netherlands. The highest area estimate of the analysed hydrogen system amounts to almost two times the land area of Texel or around 10% of the highest projected spatial use for onshore wind parks in 2050 according to the IJ3050 study. The existing main natural gas and oil pipeline network occupies around 0.5% of the total land area (about 170 km²) of the Netherlands, which is more than the maximum estimated space requirement for the hydrogen pipeline network. The spatial area requirement of the hydrogen system will be spread across the Netherlands and will not be aggregated in a single area. The amount of space that should be reserved for the hydrogen system and in which region is difficult to project as large uncertainties exist and several subsystems can likely be repurposed from existing infrastructure, such as pipelines and storage facilities. Given that the hydrogen system can partly reuse and repurpose existing subsystems and uses partly underground area, only a limited share of the 99-280 km² would likely require new, above-ground space.

Uncertainties in the analysis

The observed differences, both in the ranges that we find in our analysis and if we compare our results with the I13050 and PEH reports, can be largely explained by the uncertainties behind the analysis. Firstly, uncertainties exist in the scenarios, which differ substantially in capacities and choice for different hydrogen subsystems. Secondly, the area use for the various existing and planned facilities differs substantially and results in a broad range in specific spatial area use for the different subsystems. And finally, the designated space use is influenced by the defined area, which may include, for instance, underground area, permitted area, and/or repurposed area, or only aboveground equipment area.

Recommendations for future research

Making clear choices for the selected hydrogen subsystems, their capacities, and the type of area analysed to fulfil a specific scenario would be helpful to arrive at a more narrow bandwidth in spatial area use. The relevance of such an analysis may, however, be limited as it is at the moment highly unsure which subsystems will be implemented, in which form, at which capacity, at which locations, and how much of that can be reused or repurposed.

Once more projects of hydrogen subsystems are being deployed, the accuracy of the specific spatial footprint of these subsystems can be improved. Periodic updates of our analysis may, thus, lead to new insights. It may also be worthwhile to expand this analysis by including other systems that are impacted by the hydrogen system, such as electricity supply. Depending on how the future energy system may develop, the relative contributions of the hydrogen subsystems and their respective area requirements may also vary. This study can therefore function as a starting point for more extensive assessments on the area requirements of the entire future energy system.

Conclusions

Our estimates for the spatial footprint of the hydrogen system cover a large range. Uncertainties arise from the assumptions behind and choices made in the four I13050 scenarios that result in varying contributions of specific hydrogen subsystems. Additionally, substantial bandwidths of area requirements per hydrogen subsystem are also observed.

The total area requirements of the hydrogen system add up to 80-101 km² in 2030, 84-217 km² in 2040 and 99-280 km² in 2050. The International Trade scenario requires the most space for both the low and high estimates, while the three other scenarios require less space and do not differ significantly. Based on the system footprint assessment and the aforementioned uncertainties, we share a number of general reflections below.

The pipeline network is responsible for a large part of the system spatial footprint with a contribution of 88-125 km² in 2050. However, importantly, substantial amounts of this space will exist out of existing natural gas pipelines that are repurposed for hydrogen. The spatial footprint of underground hydrogen storage depends strongly on whether only the well and aboveground facilities are considered or the entire permitted plot size and ranges between 0.1 and 89 km² in 2050. Both pipeline corridors and hydrogen storage facilities lie (largely) underground and the aboveground area can often largely be utilized for other purposes, such as agriculture. Hydrogen refuelling stations can occupy a large area of 3–35 km² in 2050, but options exist to limit the footprint through more efficient use of space and/or by integrating hydrogen tank facilities in conventional refuelling stations.

The footprint of hydrogen import terminals is uncertain due to the variation in spatial footprint of the different hydrogen import chain options. Total area requirements for hydrogen import range from 2 to 21 km² in 2050. The specific spatial footprint ranges from relatively small for methanol storage to very large for liquid hydrogen. It is unsure what the preferred import chain will be, but area requirements may be one of the aspects to take into consideration when selecting an option. Reuse of existing terminal facilities may also limit the use of new land area. At times when demand for hydrogen cannot be supplied by production or from storage, peak import of hydrogen is required. The terminals for peak import of hydrogen add a significant footprint, while their contribution to the imported volumes of hydrogen is small. Specifying which type of hydrogen carriers will be imported, will help to improve the assessment of the spatial footprint. Alternatively, other solutions (e.g., demand response) can possibly avoid the need for peak hydrogen supply and may limit the spatial implications for hydrogen import.

The estimated maximum of 15 km² for the spatial footprint of hydrogen production is relatively modest compared to the other subsystems. Of this, the onshore electrolyzers correspond to up to 11 km² for an installed capacity of 25 GW_e. Biomass gasification has a relatively large footprint, especially considering the relatively modest amount of hydrogen produced through this route.

For the subsystems for which the I13050 or PEH studies has also made a spatial footprint estimate, our estimates are of a similar order of magnitude. The I13050 and PEH estimates tend to be on the lower side of the bandwidth of our estimates.

Despite the broad bandwidth of spatial use, the total area requirement of the analysed hydrogen system in the context of the I13050 scenarios is, in comparison to other systems, not excessive. Notably, our scope of the hydrogen system excludes energy supply, which will have a dramatic impact on the area requirements related to hydrogen production. Based on the estimated area requirements in this study, it should be well possible to implement a hydrogen system in the Netherlands under the condition that energy supply for hydrogen production will not be a constraint. This study also indicates that for most subsystems, specific choices and designs may allow for a more efficient use of the space and thereby reduce the total area requirements, especially when considering new land area.

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1. Introduction

The energy transition and the role of hydrogen

The Paris Agreement target to limit global warming to 1.5-2°C requires significant changes to the global economy. To meet the targets, the energy and industrial sector need to transition to a system with zero or low greenhouse gas (GHG) emissions. That includes reducing emissions from the production of hydrogen, which is currently used for a variety of purposes such as petroleum refining and the production of chemicals such as fertilisers. In addition, hydrogen produced from renewable electricity through water electrolysis can play a role in the future energy system as low-emission energy carrier and as a means to convert and store variable renewable electricity. The transition, thus, requires both the repurposing of existing hydrogen systems and the introduction of new systems and technologies.

What are the plans for the roll-out of hydrogen in the Netherlands?

The Netherlands is a significant hydrogen producer and consumer, second only after Germany in Europe. Existing hydrogen production is mostly from steam methane reformers (SMR) and hydrogen is used in a variety of industrial purposes as a feedstock. To reduce emissions from SMR-based hydrogen production, there are plans for the capture and storage of CO₂ (CCS) at these facilities. In addition, the Netherlands has formulated targets to build 4 GW_e of electrolyser capacity by 2030 and 8 GW_e in 2032 to produce hydrogen based on renewable electricity [1]. A national hydrogen transmission network is also being developed to link hydrogen production, import, export, and usage [2]. For the long term, various scenario studies provide a wide range of projections for hydrogen production, import, export, and use in the Netherlands up to 2050 [3] [4] [5] [6] [7]. The next chapter (Chapter 2) provides more details on the *Integrale Infrastructuurverkenning 2030-3050* (from here on I13050) scenario study as the basis of the analysis presented in this report.

What is the spatial footprint of the future hydrogen system?

The various policy targets, plans and scenario studies raise the question of what the spatial footprint will be for the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands. Several studies have already touched upon the spatial requirements of elements of the future hydrogen system. The I13050 report provides an indicative spatial assessment for the hydrogen network (both the main high pressure pipeline network – including hydrogen compression stations - and the regional medium pressure network), electrolysers, flexible (hydrogen) turbines, and the above ground spatial requirement for hydrogen storage in salt caverns and depleted natural gas fields [4]. The Main Energy Structure Programme (*Programma Energie Hoofdinfrastructuur - PEH*) also includes spatial assessments for electrolysers, flexible (hydrogen) turbines, and hydrogen import terminals [8] [9].

The goal of the analysis presented in this report is threefold:

1. Validate the assumptions for spatial requirements from the I13050 and PEH studies
2. Include new and improved spatial requirements for key subsystems of the future hydrogen system
3. Provide a spatial assessment of the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands based on the data of the I13050 scenarios

Scope of the study

The study focuses on the assessment of the spatial requirements of the hydrogen system in the Netherlands up to 2050 according to the I13050 scenarios. Several key systems required for hydrogen supply, transport, storage, and use are included in the scope of the study. Spatial footprints are determined for all the identified key subsystems. The space required for electricity production from

solar and wind power, and the capture, transport and storage of CO₂ from hydrogen production based on steam methane reforming or autothermal reforming are excluded from the scope of the study. Figure 1 provides an overview of the key subsystems covered in the analysis.

Figure 1. Overview of hydrogen system and key subsystems in scope for this study (for enlarged version: see the Appendix)

Methodology

To reach the main goal of this study, which is to provide a spatial assessment of the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands based on the data of the I13050 scenarios, first an analysis of the I13050 scenario study is performed (Chapter 2). For each of the I13050 scenarios an inventory is made of the different identified hydrogen subsystems and their capacities. In all calculations, we have used the lower heating value of hydrogen (120 MJ/kg). Next, the spatial footprint of each of these hydrogen subsystems is determined, either by validation of the already reported values from the I13050 report, or by consultation of other reports and data sources (Chapter 3). In several cases, the findings are further substantiated by analysis of the geographical surface area of existing projects on the map. In Chapter 4, the total area requirements are determined for each of the scenarios. This is achieved by connecting the capacities of the hydrogen subsystems with the specific footprint of these subsystems. The results and implications thereof are also presented and discussed in this chapter before the report is finalized with some conclusions.

2. Scenarios and plans

2.1 The IP2024 and I13050 scenarios

In the I13050 study, four climate-neutral energy scenarios for 2050 are outlined [3] [4]. The scenarios vary on the scale of individually versus collectively-driven technology choices, government-driven action versus market-driven solutions, national orientation versus international orientation, and import-oriented versus as self-sufficient as possible. The four scenarios are:

1. **Decentral Initiatives (DEC)**. Nationally oriented, market-driven, and individual technology choices. Strong reduction in energy-intensive industry. Very high level of renewable energy production.
2. **National Leadership (NAT)**. Nationally oriented, collective solutions, and government-driven action. Limited reduction in energy-intensive industry and deployment of new industry based on synthetic molecules (from hydrogen and CO₂).
3. **European Integration (EUR)**. Internationally oriented, collective solutions, and government-driven action. Limited reduction in energy-intensive industry and deployment of new industry based on synthetic molecules (from hydrogen and CO₂).
4. **International Trade (INT)**. Internationally oriented, market-driven, and individual technology choices. More room for imports.

For the modelled years of 2030 and 2040, the scenarios of I13050 have been made consistent with the final situation for the 2050 scenarios. For the period up to 2035, Netbeheer Nederland has also developed alternative scenarios for the making of investment plans by the Dutch gas and electricity grid operators (shortened to IP2024) [10]. These scenarios are:

1. **Climate Ambition (KA)**. The central scenario based on existing and planned policy (based on the Climate and Energy Outlook 2022 [11]) and supplemented with policy proposals from the Climate Agreement [12].
2. **National Drivers (ND)**. Scenario with stronger electrification and renewable electricity production on land than the central scenario.
3. **International Ambition (IA)**. Scenario with higher contribution of renewable gasses, such as green gas and hydrogen.

The scenarios from the IP2024 and I13050 coincide in the period 2030-2040. As illustrated in Figure 2, the ND IP scenario best fits into the DEC and NAT I13050 scenarios, the KA IP scenario into the NAT and EUR I13050 scenarios, and the IA IP scenario into the EUR and INT I13050 scenarios.

Figure 2. Links between the IP2024 and II3050 scenarios [4].

2.1.1 Hydrogen production and trade in the IP2024 and II3050 scenarios

The IP2024 and II3050 scenarios each contain different assumptions on the production, trade, and use of hydrogen. The different assumptions have an impact on the spatial requirements. Therefore, an overview of the main differences is given in Table 1.

Table 1. Overview hydrogen production, trade, and use in the IP2024 and II3050 scenarios.

Scenario	Hydrogen production	Hydrogen trade	Hydrogen use
IP2024 – KA	4 GW electrolysis based on Climate Agreement	Net export	- Industry - Transport
IP2024 – ND	Electrolysis important to provide flexibility to the energy system with high variable renewable electricity production	Net export	- Industry
IP 2024 - IA	Green hydrogen production based on growth of offshore wind and solar PV capacity	More significant imports than the other IP2024 scenarios in 2030. Limited net export	- Industry - Transport - Electricity
II3050 – DEC	Local green hydrogen production	Net import in 2040 and net export in 2050	- Industry - Heating in buildings (limited)
II3050 – EUR	Mix of green and blue hydrogen (natural gas reforming + CCS)	Imports and exports	- Existing and new industry - Transport (limited) - Heating in buildings (limited) - Electricity
II3050 – NAT	Green hydrogen production large - important for balancing energy system	Net export	- New industry - Transport (limited) - Electricity
II3050 - INT	Electrolysis coupled to offshore wind	Significant imports and exports. Higher import than export	- Industry - Transport - Heating in buildings, district heating and agricultural sector - Electricity

An overview of the hydrogen production and import capacities are given in Figure 3. There are two types of electrolyzers included in the model: flexible electrolyzers on land and electrolyzers directly

coupled to offshore wind energy. The offshore electrolyzers follow the wind energy production profile. In both cases, the electrolyzers do not operate at full load and the installed capacity is, thus, larger than if baseload production is assumed. The amount of full load hours the electrolyzers produce depends on the scenario, varying between 3700 and 5500 hours for onshore electrolyzers and between 4000 and 4800 hours for offshore electrolyzers.

The other hydrogen production technologies, such as steam methane reforming with CCS and biomass gasification, are assumed to operate all year at full capacity. Another large share of hydrogen supply in the scenarios comes from import. For hydrogen import there is both baseload capacity and peak capacity included in the scenarios. The peak capacity is relatively large, yet is only responsible for a small part of the import volumes. In the Energy Transition Model (ETM), which is used to simulate the II3050 scenarios, the peak import is used as a final option to match hydrogen demand and supply. For a few days per year, typically in February but in some of the scenarios also in April, May and December, the peak hydrogen import is utilised once the underground hydrogen storage capacity is depleted. As a result there is a high peak use of the import terminals of up to 41 GW_{H₂} on top of the baseload terminals (see Figure 3), while the imported volumes remain relatively limited (see Figure 4). While other configurations should be possible to balance the supply and demand of hydrogen over the year (e.g., larger underground hydrogen storage capacity, larger and more flexible production, or a reduction in demand), such options are not further analysed here.

Figure 3. Hydrogen production and import capacities in the IP2024 and II3050 scenarios for 2030, 2040 and 2050. Industry – residual gasses refers to residual hydrogen from industrial processes (e.g. steam crackers) or from reformed methane-rich residual gasses (e.g. from refining). Note that the electrolysis capacity is utilised flexibly based on the production of renewable electricity, but for the other capacities baseload import or production is assumed in the Energy Transition Model.

The scenarios express the import capacity in terms of hydrogen. It is unclear whether the hydrogen is imported in gaseous form (by pipeline or ship), in liquid form (by ship), or as hydrogen carrier (for

instance, as ammonia or liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC)). Ammonia and compressed hydrogen are mentioned in the scenario report as the most likely transport means in the short term, while (liquid) hydrogen shipping is expected to play a role on the longer term [3].

The scenarios also assume different contributions of hydrogen production through steam methane reforming (SMR). In all scenarios, the CO₂ from the SMR process is captured and stored (CCS). Lastly there is some hydrogen produced through biomass gasification and from residual gasses from industry. In the scenarios, both biomass gasification and residual gasses reforming are also combined with CCS.

In the ETM, most assets operate at full capacity. As a consequence, the baseload import capacities correspond, at least in some of the scenarios, to a significant amount of hydrogen import (see dark green area in Figure 4). The figure also shows that hydrogen production through SMR (yellow area) is relatively important in 2030, after which its role decreases relative to hydrogen production through electrolysis and imports. Only in the European Integration scenario in 2050, it has a relatively large contribution at 56 TWh/year (25% of total supply). The role of electrolysis grows in time in all scenarios. The split between flexible electrolysis and dedicated electrolysis linked to offshore wind (blue and striped blue area, respectively) differs per scenario. In the internationally oriented scenarios (IA, EUR and INT), the most significant imports and exports of hydrogen can be observed. For this analysis we assume that hydrogen is mainly exported to Germany and Belgium over land via the hydrogen pipeline network and, thus, no additional space is required specifically for export.

Figure 4. Production, import, and export of hydrogen in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios.

2.1.2 Underground hydrogen storage in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios

The amount of underground hydrogen storage capacity required also varies per scenario and by weather year [4]. For the present analysis, we consider the minimum and maximum storage requirements based on an analysis done for the I13050 for the different scenario's and for weather

years between 1990 and 2019 (see Figure 5). The maximum storage capacity required in 2050 is 60 TWh. In addition, the scenarios include methane storage that decreases up to a maximum of 30 TWh in 2050. The storage of hydrogen and methane together would require 275 salt caverns [4]. This is significantly more than the six caverns used today for natural gas storage and the maximum of 60 caverns that TNO and EBN indicate are possible to realise by 2050 [13]. The I13050 study estimates how the storage requirement can be split between salt caverns and depleted gas fields. The two storage options can serve different purposes: salt caverns are more suitable for short-term highly-flexible storage and depleted gas fields are best suited for seasonal storage. Moreover, the total storage capacity required increases slightly as there will be times when one of the types of stores is releasing hydrogen while the other is filling up [4].

Only the results for minimum and maximum storage requirements in 2050 in a combination of salt caverns and depleted gas fields are shared in the I13050 report. The minimum storage capacity is 4 TWh in depleted gas fields and 2 TWh in salt caverns. The total of 6 TWh is 14% lower than the minimum in 2050 in Figure 5 (in the European Integration scenario). The maximum storage capacity required is 56 TWh in depleted gas fields and 16 TWh in salt caverns, totalling 72 TWh (22% higher than the maximum for the International Ambition scenario in Figure 5).

For the spatial analysis in Chapter 4, the weather-year-based ranges in Figure 5 are used to estimate minimum and maximum spatial requirements for hydrogen storage. We have not made an estimate for the minimum and maximum storage requirement with a split between salt caverns and depleted gas fields.

Figure 5. Underground hydrogen storage capacity in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios. Only the 2050 datapoints are shared in the I13050 report. The 2030 and 2040 minima and maxima have been estimated for this study.

2.1.3 Hydrogen use in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios

There are multiple applications for which hydrogen is used in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios. The main hydrogen user throughout the scenarios is industry (see brown area in Figure 6). Hydrogen is used in industry for both energetic (e.g. as fuel in burners) and non-energetic purposes (i.e. as a feedstock to produce fuels and chemicals). Other sectors with a significant hydrogen use are transport

and electricity production, both in combined cycle gas turbines (CCGT) and in gas turbines (GT). In the European Integration and International Trade scenarios hydrogen is also used for heating in buildings and households. Only in the international scenarios, a limited amount of hydrogen is also used for heating in the agriculture sector and for district heating.

Figure 6. Overview of hydrogen demand for various sectors in the IP2024 and II3050 scenarios.

The demand for hydrogen in various sectors varies throughout the year, for example, based on the weather conditions for heating in buildings and households. For the spatial requirement assessment, the maximum demand within the year is used as a proxy for the installed capacities (see Figure 7).

Out of the hydrogen demand technologies, we have only assessed the spatial requirements for the gas turbines and for hydrogen fuel stations for transport. Spatial requirements for hybrid heat pumps, industrial and agricultural burners, fuels and chemicals production, and hydrogen heaters for district heating have not been assessed. It is expected that the low pressure hydrogen distribution network required to supply hydrogen in the built environment and decentralised industry (referred to as the sixth industrial cluster of the Netherlands) will have the most significant spatial impact, but there is currently insufficient information available on the future distribution network to properly address these assumptions.

Approximated installed capacities for hydrogen demand - IP2024 and I13050 scenarios

Figure 7. Overview of peak hydrogen demand for various applications in the IP2024 and I13050 scenarios.

2.1.4 Hydrogen infrastructure in the I13050 scenarios

As previously indicated, the I13050 study provides an estimate for the spatial footprint of the hydrogen high pressure pipeline network (HTL), including compressor stations, and for the regional medium pressure pipeline network (RTL). The estimate is based on an assumed length of pipelines required in 2035 and 2050 (see Table 2). The starting point is the assumption that a large part of the hydrogen HTL network has been realised by 2035. In the four scenarios, there is an additional amount of HTL pipeline network required, ranging from 80 to 260 kilometres. In the European Integration and International Trade scenarios, there is an additional length of RTL pipelines of less than 2000 kilometres and less than 3000 kilometres expected, respectively. The total amount of kilometres of hydrogen pipeline in 2050 is lower than the current natural gas pipeline network, which spans around 12000 kilometres, half of which is HTL and the other half RTL [14]. Next to the hydrogen network, the I13050 also expects there to be an operational (green) methane network.

Table 2. Overview of hydrogen network infrastructure in the I13050 scenarios

Subsystem	Unit	Situation in 2035	DEC 2050	EUR 2050	NAT 2050	INT 2050
HTL pipelines	km	1100	1250	1180	1250	1360
RTL pipelines	km	0	0	<2000	0	<3000
Compressor stations	#	Unknown	4	3	4	7

According to I13050, the majority of the compressor stations for the hydrogen network will be placed at the locations where compressor stations for the natural gas network currently exist, as the natural gas network will be repurposed. The I13050 report outlines that in 2050 a total of seven additional compressor stations are required for the high pressure network (HTL). There is also one compressor required in 2040 in Brabant that is no longer necessary in 2050 due to lower assumed exports to Belgium in 2050 compared to 2040. Of these compressor stations, I13050 expects only 1-2 to be placed in new locations and the spatial footprint to therefore be limited (<0.01 km²).

3. Hydrogen systems

Based on the scenarios, we define the hydrogen system and several subsystems, which we categorize according to their application, i.e. facilities that support the supply, transport, storage, and use of hydrogen. In section 3.1, first the scope of the analysed hydrogen system is explained and next (section 3.2) each of the subsystems is described in more detail. In the descriptions of the subsystems, the main focus is to explain how we assessed the spatial footprint which is expected to be necessary for the implementation of the specific facility. A summary of the spatial requirements of the analysed subsystems is provided in section 0.

3.1 Hydrogen system and subsystems

To determine the scope of the spatial footprint analysis, a hydrogen system is outlined in which several key subsystems required for hydrogen supply, transport, storage, and use are included, largely based on the II3050 scenarios. The main focus is to analyse the amount of land area that will be required for the total hydrogen system. Hydrogen can be supplied by domestic production or through import. Various production technologies exist, of which we include steam methane or autothermal reforming (SMR/ATR), water electrolysis (both on- and offshore) and biomass gasification, which are all covered in the II3050 scenarios. Other production routes, such as methane pyrolysis or dry methane reforming, can also supply hydrogen but are not covered in II3050 and thus excluded from our scope. Offshore hydrogen production through electrolysis is included, mainly for comparative reasons, although no land area is required for this subsystem. Besides production, hydrogen can also be imported. Import is assumed to mainly occur across seas (not via the pipeline system). Only the total and not the specific type of hydrogen import is quantified in the II3050 scenarios. It is only mentioned that ammonia and (liquid) hydrogen shipping are expected to play a role. This analysis covers multiple options to import hydrogen, either direct as liquid hydrogen or in the form of a carrier, such as ammonia, methanol, liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC), or biomass, via import terminals and (if necessary) conversion facilities. Notably, in this study ammonia, methanol and biomass are categorised as hydrogen carriers and only utilised to supply hydrogen. In reality, both ammonia, methanol and biomass can be used for other purposes as well, for instance as feedstock for the chemical industry or directly as fuel. Compressed hydrogen or other hydrogen carriers [15], such as metal hydrides, may also play a role in the hydrogen system but are excluded from this study.

The hydrogen subsystems are connected and rely on other systems, such as electricity infrastructure and the supply, transport and storage of CO₂. These other systems also require space but are not further analysed in this study as is indicated in the scheme (*Figure 8*).

Once the hydrogen is produced or imported, it should be transported to the end user. Hydrogen can be transported and distributed via a pipeline system or by trucks or tube trailers. In the Netherlands, thanks to the option to (partly) repurpose the natural gas network, pipelines are most likely to cover the dominant share of hydrogen transport. Tanker trucks, including their loading and unloading stations, are left out of scope, because a rather limited role is expected for these transport options. The pipeline network, including several stations which ensure the proper injection, metering, pressure regulation and export of hydrogen, is in scope. Offshore pipelines are not analysed as these do not use land area. The storage of hydrogen can be facilitated underground in salt caverns and depleted gas fields and aboveground in storage tanks. The latter category is left out of scope as it is currently difficult to assess where hydrogen will be produced and used and how much of that is stored locally.

Figure 8. Block diagram of the analysed hydrogen system and key subsystems (identical to Figure 1)

Hydrogen can be used in several applications, either as fuel or as a chemical feedstock. Currently, hydrogen is mainly used in industry. It is expected that part of natural gas use by industry can also be replaced by hydrogen. Possibly, the same burners, furnaces, and equipment can be used and no additional area is needed, but for some applications this may be different. As we could not find any data on the spatial implications of replacing (part of) natural gas use in industry by hydrogen, we excluded this subsystem from our analysis. Hydrogen use as feedstock for synthetic fuel and chemicals production is also outside the scope of this work. Hydrogen as fuel for mobility can, for instance, play a role in fuel cell electric vehicles. To fuel these vehicles, refuelling stations should be equipped with hydrogen tanking installations. Hydrogen in the built environment might take over (part of) the role of natural gas, e.g. to fuel hybrid heat pumps or gas boilers. This subsystem is not further analysed as we assume that such systems are already or will be mainly installed in buildings and do not occupy additional land area. Another end use application which is described in the I13050 scenarios is the use of hydrogen as a fuel in power plants for electricity production.

3.2 Description of subsystems

In the following subsections, each of the hydrogen subsystems will be described in terms of their role in the overall hydrogen system and their spatial footprint is assessed.

3.2.1 Hydrogen production facilities – electrolyser

In the scenarios, two types of electrolysers are mentioned, either on land or offshore, coupled to wind energy. Electrolysers are expected to play an important role in the hydrogen value chain and different types of electrolyser technologies are being developed. Several types of electrolysers already exist, of which the alkaline and proton exchange membrane (PEM) electrolysers are most common. These technologies have achieved a high level of maturity and their technology readiness level (TRL) is typically considered 8 to 9. However, GW-scale facilities have not yet been deployed and ongoing developments seek to further enhance the scale-up, performance, and efficiency. Advanced alkaline electrolysers are undergoing refinement, targeting operational improvements at high current densities using non-noble cathode coatings, like Raney Nickel or Ni-oxides [16]. Similarly, PEM electrolyser technology is evolving, with future stack designs projected to substantially outperform existing

configurations, aiming for higher current densities, improved efficiency, and enhanced durability [16]. These advancements are not only crucial to improve the performance and sustainability of the process, but could also reduce the spatial requirements in the future.

An electrolyser facility consists of various components that together operate within defined spatial boundaries. Starting from input to output, these include electricity transformers and rectifiers for power conversion, electrolyser parks housing PEM or alkaline stacks, demineralization facilities for water purification, heat exchangers, cooling towers for thermal management, hydrogen gas/liquid separators, compressors for pressurization, deoxidizers, and driers [16]. The total footprint of these components together will determine the overall spatial area of an electrolyser facility. As already mentioned, the II3050 scenarios indicate the amount of hydrogen produced either onshore or offshore by electrolysis, but do not describe which type of electrolyser is used. Below the spatial differences between large and smaller scale facilities are described, along with a subsection on offshore electrolysis.

3.2.1.1 Large-scale electrolyser

Large-scale (GW_e) electrolyser plants for both PEM and alkaline systems have not yet been built and footprint data is derived from ongoing development projects, like Shell Holland Hydrogen 1 [17] and the insights presented in the Hydrohub study about the design of a "One-Gigawatt Green-Hydrogen Plant" [16]. The Shell project in the Tweede Maasvlakte in Rotterdam involves deploying a large-scale alkaline electrolysis system with a capacity of 200 MW_e and is expected to produce around 60 tonnes of hydrogen per day. The plant will use renewable electricity from an offshore wind farm in the North Sea and the hydrogen produced is expected to initially be used in the Shell Energy and Chemicals Park Rotterdam. The facility is anticipated to occupy an area of 4 hectares (including surrounding areas not primarily related to production facilities – e.g., green areas – see *Figure 9* **Error! Reference source not found.**) [17]. The space allocated to electrolyser equipment is expected to occupy around 2 ha [18]. This leads to a spatial footprint of 10-20 ha/ GW_e . The Hydrohub study estimates a spatial requirement of 17 ha for the design of a 1 GW_e alkaline system and 14 ha for the design of a 1 GW_e PEM system. It is expected for this to decrease to 10 ha for an advanced 1 GW_e electrolyser design for 2030 [16], leading to a similar spatial footprint range of 10-17 ha/ GW_e for large-scale electrolyser systems.

Figure 9. Plan for Shell Holland Hydrogen 1 200 MW_e facility [17]

In China, a few large-scale facilities have been constructed during the last years, for example, the Sinopec 260 MW_e electrolyser in Kuqa (Figure 10) [19]. In this pilot project, solar power drives the electrolysis, which is expected to produce around 20,000 tons per annum of green hydrogen. As can be seen in the figure, the facility also includes a hydrogen storage capacity of 210,000 cubic meters of hydrogen [20]. The total area of the facility (incl. storage) covers around 11 ha, which corresponds to

44 ha/GW_e. This is twice the footprint of the Shell Holland Hydrogen 1 facility and indicates the large uncertainty in assessing a specific spatial footprint, as it likely strongly depends on land availability and cost as well as the plant design and system boundaries (e.g. which components are included).

Figure 10. Sinopec electrolyser facility in Kuqa (Google Earth; date: 2022, coordinates: 41°44'33"N 83°04'41"E)

3.2.1.2 Small-scale electrolyser

Small-scale systems (with capacities of around 10 MW_e) may also play an important role in the energy transition and the development of the hydrogen network. Large-scale electrolysers are more likely to be connected to large-scale renewable electricity production sites, such as offshore wind parks. Small-scale electrolysers can instead offer flexibility and versatility for more decentralized projects (e.g., connected to solar farms) and enable production closer to the point of hydrogen use.

The total spatial footprint for both PEM and alkaline systems is based on the area requirements of demonstration projects like Demo4Grid, FEST green electrolyser gEL600, and the SinneWetterstof project. The Demo4Grid project in Austria involves deploying a 4 MW pressurized alkaline electrolysis system for grid balancing services and hydrogen supply for the neighboring MPreis bakery and meat processing, with possible supply to the mobility sector in the future [21]. The facility went into operation in January 2022 [22]. Based on Figure 11 (right), it is estimated that the Demo4Grid electrolyser site occupies an area of 0.85ha, leading to a spatial requirement of 208 ha/GW. FEST provides 2MW (gEL400) and 3MW (gEL600) integrated PEM electrolysis systems with a standard footprint of 20x18m [23]. Based on these dimensions, the spatial area requirement is estimated to be 0.036 ha with a spatial footprint of 12ha/GW. The system can produce up to 54kg/h of hydrogen [24]. FEST electrolyser systems are being used in multiple locations, including Austria for city bus refilling, Germany for refueling of commercial vehicles, and more [24] [25]. The SinneWetterstof project in the Netherlands is connected to a neighboring 50 MW solar park, where excess solar energy is converted into green hydrogen. The pilot project started in March 2022 and is a collaboration between Alliander and GroenLeven. The electrolyser system has a capacity of 1.4 MW and is expected to produce around 100 tpa of hydrogen. The hydrogen produced will be used in hydrogen filling stations. The spatial footprint is estimated at 0.2 ha, as shown in Figure 13, with a spatial requirement of 140 ha/GW [26] [27]. For further details, see also Figure 11 to Figure 13 and Table 3.

Figure 11. A: Demo4Grid plot of land for the small-scale 4 MW alkaline electrolyser (coordinates: 47°15'28.79"N, 11°18'46.70"E) [21]

Figure 12. B: FEST green electrolyser project picture [24]

Figure 13. C: SinneWetterstof project plot and project pictures for a 1.4 MW small-scale electrolyser (coordinates: 52°58'28.24"N, 6°18'9.65"E) [26]

The spatial footprint for the above small-scale electrolyser systems ranges from 12-208 ha/GW_e. It can be noted that the spatial requirement for FEST gEL600 is substantially smaller than that of the other two systems discussed above, as the spatial footprint for the FEST system is based only on the unit size and does not include the surrounding plot area. This was explored further by examining the spatial requirement of the Green Hydrogen Systems upcoming HyProvide X-Series electrolyser container units of 6 MW_e pressurized alkaline electrolyser modules [28]. This compact system will require around 0.1 ha for a site configuration of 24 MW_e and is expected to produce 10.3 tonnes of hydrogen per day [29]. This results in a spatial requirement of 4.5 ha/GW_e, which is also significantly less than when the

surrounding plot area is included. Sparsely used plot space for small-scale systems, as seen in the plot map for the SinneWeterstof project, could potentially be optimized to accommodate greater electrolyser capacity within the same plot area if space is a key constraint.

3.2.1.3 Offshore electrolyser

A compact modular design can reduce spatial footprint, especially when such systems can be installed on several floors. This is especially important when space is scarce or very costly, for instance, for offshore applications. Offshore electrolysis can be of interest to reduce spatial requirements on land for both the hydrogen and electricity system. No projects exist yet, but soon the concept will be demonstrated in the PosHYdon project [30]. In this project, a PEM electrolyser system with a capacity of 1.25 MW_e will be installed on an offshore platform to produce 400 kg of hydrogen per day from offshore wind energy [31] [32]. The system is incorporated in several containers, which cover a spatial footprint of around 0.012 ha if stacked next to each other. This leads to a specific spatial footprint of 9.6 ha/GW_e. Designs for large-scale offshore systems, as in the North Sea Energy study [33], estimate that 500 MW_e of PEM capacity can be implemented on a single offshore platform and it is anticipated that the electrolyser systems can be integrated on several floors. Such a capacity on a platform with a geographical surface area of 40 x 80 m [33] results in a specific spatial footprint of 0.64 ha/GW_e. Implementing this design over several floors can increase the area availability, while the geographical spatial footprint remains the same. If such a design can become reality, it should also be possible to build such an area-efficient facility on land when space is a limiting factor. Alternatively, offshore electrolysis is also foreseen on (artificial) energy islands [34] [33]. The spatial use for electrolysis on such islands will likely be less efficient than on a platform, but more efficient compared to onshore facilities.

3.2.1.4 Overview electrolyser spatial footprint

Below in Table 3, an overview of the collected electrolyser data is provided.

Table 3. Electrolyser spatial parameters

	Electrolyser type	Capacity MW _e	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _e	Source
Shell Holland Hydrogen 1	Alkaline	200	2-4	10-20	[17] [18]
Hydrohub design 2020	Alkaline	1000	17	17	[16]
Hydrohub design 2020	PEM	1000	14	14	[16]
Hydrohub design 2030	Alkaline/PEM	1000	10	10	[16]
Sinopec Kuqa	Alkaline	260	11	44	[20] [19]
Demo4Grid	Alkaline	4	0.85	208	[21]
FEST gEL600	PEM	3	0.036	12	[23]
SinneWetterstof	Alkaline	1.4	0.2	140	[27]
GHS HyProvide X-Series	Alkaline	24	0.1	4.5	[29]
PosHYdon	PEM	1.25	0.012	10	[30] [32]
North Sea Energy design	PEM	500	0.32	0.6	[33]
Selected range					
Onshore Electrolyser (large-scale)	Alkaline/PEM	-	-	10-44	[17] [20]
Onshore Electrolyser (small-scale)	Alkaline/PEM	-	-	4.5-208	[21] [29]
Offshore Electrolyser	PEM	-	-	0.6-10	[30] [33]

The broad range in specific area usage for the different studies and projects indicates that the spatial footprint required for electrolysis is uncertain and likely depends on the application and location. The selected range for onshore electrolyzers is determined at 10-44 ha/GW_e (low/high case), which will be used to analyse the total footprint for electrolyzers on land based on the different scenarios. This covers values used in the spatial analysis in the PEH study, i.e. 10 ha/GW_e [8], and the II3050 report [3], in which an area of 3 GW_e/km² (~33 ha/GW_e) is mentioned for power-to-gas. Although it does not involve land area, the spatial footprint for offshore electrolyzers have also been analysed separately and results in a range of 0.6-10 ha/GW_e. This value can be used to estimate the number of platforms or island area that would be required to supply a specific amount of hydrogen offshore.

3.2.2 Hydrogen production facilities – steam methane and autothermal reforming

Steam methane reforming (SMR) is already a widely used method for hydrogen production from natural gas. This process occurs within a reformer, where steam reacts with natural gas at elevated temperatures. The SMR plant typically incorporates a COGEN (Combined Heat and Power) plant to export a fraction of the energy to the electricity grid [35]. In the steam reforming process, hydrocarbons, predominantly methane in natural gas, are catalytically converted into hydrogen and carbon monoxide by reaction with steam. This method is considered the most common and efficient means of producing pure hydrogen. SMR usually utilizes nickel catalysts and operates at temperatures up to 1200°C. The energy efficiency typically ranges between 74% to 85% based on the lower heating value (LHV) of hydrogen, with a potential production capacity ranging from 1,350 to 18,000 kg/h of hydrogen (45 – 600 MW_{H₂}) [36]. At a scaled-up SMR plant, various subsystems and components operate within the defined spatial boundaries of the production plant. The overall SMR process consists of the following facilities/components: natural gas desulphurization and pre-treatment plant; natural gas reformer; heat recovery steam generator; water-gas shift reactor, CO₂ adsorption; dryer and hydrogen separation, and purification in a pressure swing adsorption unit [36].

The spatial footprint of SMR is based on existing facilities, namely, Air Products Nederland B.V. Pernis and Air Liquide Nederland SMR2, located in Rotterdam, the Netherlands. These facilities have a production capacity of 106 and 114 kiloton hydrogen per year and emit between 760 and 810 kilotons of CO₂ annually [36]. The geographical area occupied by the plants was determined to be approximately 2.3 and 10 hectares, respectively, as shown in Figure 14 [37].

Figure 14. A: Aerial View of Air Products Nederland B.V. SMR Facility at Botlekweg, Netherlands (coordinates: 51°52'11.27"N, 4°17'14.48"E) and B: Air Liquide Nederland B.V. (SMR2) (coordinates: 51°53'22.14"N 4°15'7.52"E)

Autothermal reforming (ATR) is a method for hydrogen production in which partial oxidation (POX) and steam methane reforming (SMR) is combined in a single reactor operating at temperatures ranging from 900 to 1150°C. This approach allows for more efficient heat management and yields more

hydrogen compared to only POX, while also providing faster start-up and response times than only SMR [38]. Initially, ATR systems comprised separate burner and steam reformer units, but advancements have led to single-unit designs. However, the catalyst employed in these systems must be compatible with both the steam reforming and partial oxidation reactions, presenting a significant technical challenge. Various catalyst formulations, including copper- and noble metal-based catalysts, have been developed to address these challenges [39]. In scaled-up ATR plants, the system boundaries encompass the input of water and electricity and the output of pressurized hydrogen and co-products. The spatial analysis of ATR systems considers several critical components essential for the production process. These components include the air separation unit, heater, hydrogenation reactor, sulphur absorber, pre-reformer, autothermal reformer, heat exchanger, final cooling and separation units, and (optionally) a carbon capture and storage facility [40]. The ATR process is typically combined with a follow-up reaction in which, for instance, methanol, ammonia, or gasoline are produced. The Topsoe SynCOR reactor in the gas-to-gasoline plant operated by Rönesans in Turkmenistan, serves as a reference for a one-step hydrogen production process. Spatial requirements for this facility, with a production capacity of 1.9 million tons of methanol per year and 240 kilotons of hydrogen per year, occupy approximately 13.5 hectares (See Figure 15) [41] [37]. There are other facilities within the same production plant, which sums up to a 72.5 ha plot size, but these facilities relate to hydrogen and methanol to gasoline processes.

Figure 15. Aerial view showing the delimitation of the SynCOR Plant Area in Turkmenistan, Operated by Rönesans. The delimited area A represents the space requirement for the ATR operation (coordinates: 38°15'24.27"N, 58°23'38.00"E) [37].

Table 4. Spatial requirements for SMR and ATR plants

	Reformer type	Capacity kt/yr	Year	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H2}	Source
Air Products Nederland	SMR	106	2021	2.3	5	[36]
Air Liquide Nederland	SMR	114	2021	10	21	[36]
Topsoe SynCOR-ATR	ATR	240	2022	13.5	14	[41]
Selected range	SMR/ATR	-	>2030	-	5-21	[36]

Both SMR and ATR technology is highly advanced and is commercially available at large scale with a TRL of 9 [35] [38]. Less experience exists when CCS technology has to be integrated, but both CO₂ capture and storage have been demonstrated at large scale. The main spatial requirement at the site of the SMR/ATR plant is the CO₂ capture and compression equipment, as well as some pipelines for CO₂ transport. We expect that within the plot area of the SMR/ATR plants there will likely be enough

space accessible for the installation of such assets, based on the already broad range estimated and shown in Table 4. ATR and SMR facilities are expected to have a similar spatial footprint, as confirmed by this analysis (Table 4).

3.2.3 Hydrogen production facilities – biomass gasification

Biomass gasification is a process in which biomass or waste materials are gasified into a mixture of hydrogen, carbon monoxide, and carbon dioxide known as synthesis gas (syngas). Syngas can be utilized as fuel for the production of electricity. Syngas can also be reformed with steam to produce hydrogen, as considered in the I13050 scenarios. Alternatively, the biogenic carbon in the syngas can also be used to produce various carbon-based biofuels such as methanol or synthetic hydrocarbons [42]. The gasification technology allows for the utilization of a wide range of feedstocks, including agricultural residues, forestry waste, municipal solid waste, and dedicated energy crops, thereby minimizing competition with food production. Gasification is recognized for its high overall energy conversion efficiency, typically ranging from 40% to 65% on an energy basis [43]. Critical components essential for the production process include the biomass feedstock handling system, pyrolysis reactor, gasification unit, gas cleaning and tar removal system, gas conditioning unit, reformer, and (optionally) a fuel synthesis reactor. Emissions from biomass gasification are not counted as (fossil) CO₂ emissions, but carbon capture facilities may also be integrated into the plant design to use or store the generated CO₂. Current commercial developments in biomass gasification technology showcase advancements in process efficiency and reliability, with several operational and planned projects worldwide. These projects utilize various gasification technologies, including fluidized bed and entrained flow gasifiers, demonstrating technology readiness levels (TRL) ranging from 6 to 9 [42]. Additionally, ongoing projects by companies like LanzaTech, Fulcrum, and ENI-controlled ventures signify the growing interest and investment in biomass gasification for sustainable fuel production.

The spatial requirements for biomass gasification plants are estimated based on operational gasification facilities, which do not directly produce hydrogen but a syngas that is used for other applications (see Figure 16). The Vaasa bio-gasification plant in Finland, with a capacity of 140 MW_{in}, uses biogas to generate electricity. The site contains multiple power plants of approximately 0.7 GW of total capacity and occupies approximately 13 hectares of which we allocate 2.5 ha (roughly 20%) to the biomass storage and gasification process (Table 5) [44] [37]. Assuming a biomass to hydrogen efficiency of 46% [45], this corresponds to a 64 MW_{H₂} plant and results in a spatial footprint of 39 ha/GW_{H₂}. In the UK, the ABSL Swindon Plant demonstrates the production of biomethane through waste gasification with an input capacity of 8000 tonnes of waste per year and 22 GWh of product output per year [46]. That equals a capacity of 3 MW_{H₂}. The plot size spans an area of 1.0 hectare, resulting in a specific footprint area of 332 ha/GW_{H₂} [47]. The capacity of these two projects differs substantially, which results in a footprint range of 39 and 332 ha/GW_{H₂}. Due to adjustment to (locally) available feedstock, the capacity of biomass gasification facilities may in reality also cover a relatively wide range. To provide insight into the spatial footprint associated with different production capacities, the full range is explored as our low to high estimate. It should be noted that this specific spatial footprint significantly surpasses that of other hydrogen production technologies, but it does also include storage capacity for biomass feedstock.

Figure 16. Aerial view showing the delimitation of the A-Vaasa Bio-Gasification Plant area in Finland, B- ABSL - Swindon Plant UK (coordinates: A: 63° 5'27.47"N, 21°33'7.90"E ; B: 51°35'48.02"N, 1°44'27.30"W)

Table 5. Biomass gasification production space and production parameters

	Current use	Capacity MW _{H2}	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H2}	Source
Vaasa Bio-Gasification Plant	Electricity production	64	2.5	39	[44]
ABSL - Swindon Demoplant	Biomethane production	3	1.0	332	[47]
Selected range		-	-	39-332	[44] [47]

3.2.4 Hydrogen import – liquid hydrogen import and storage

Import is expected to form a large part of the hydrogen required to meet the demand in Northwest Europe [48] [49]. Hydrogen can be imported in compressed or liquified form, or using hydrogen carriers, such as ammonia, liquid organic hydrogen carriers (LOHCs), and methanol, as this makes the hydrogen easier to transport [15] [50] [51]. For transportation in liquid form, hydrogen is cooled and stored at -253 °C [52]. This results in a reduced volume and higher volumetric density when compared to hydrogen gas. Liquifying hydrogen is more energy intensive than compressing hydrogen gas and has associated boil-off losses, as well as high liquefaction costs. Liquid hydrogen has mainly been used for specific applications in the past, like space travel [52] [53]. To estimate the spatial requirement for liquid hydrogen storage and import infrastructure, storage facilities from NASA and import facilities from the Kobe import terminal in Japan are analysed.

Currently, the world’s largest liquid hydrogen storage tank is housed at launch pad 39B at the NASA Kennedy Space Center in Florida [54] (Figure 17, right). The facility also includes two smaller liquid hydrogen storage tanks with a joint capacity of 3,200 m³ constructed in the 1960’s [55]. The new spherical tank has a useable capacity of 4,732 m³ and was constructed by CB&I in 2022 [54] (Figure 17, left). The tank utilizes a glass bubble insulation system and an integrated helium refrigeration system developed by NASA to minimise boil-off [54] [55] [56]. CB&I now offer larger liquid hydrogen storage tanks of 40,000 m³ and are aiming to develop tanks with industry partners up to 100,000 m³ [56]. The spatial footprint of the new NASA liquid hydrogen storage tank is determined to be 0.32 ha. The volumetric capacity of liquid hydrogen storage is expected to handle approximately 12 kton of H₂ per year, assuming the tank has a similar throughput factor as the OCI ammonia import terminal (see section 3.2.5). The specific spatial footprint amounts to 6.8 ha/GW_{H2}.

Figure 17. Aerial view and spatial footprint of the NASA liquid hydrogen storage tanks at the Kennedy Space Center (Google Earth, coordinates: 28°37'48"N 80°37'05"W, data attribution: 1/15/2022) [37]

A pilot liquid hydrogen import terminal was developed in 2020 by Kawasaki in Kobe, Japan. This included a 2,500 m³ spherical storage tank, a loading/unloading arm for transferring the hydrogen from ships to the terminal at low temperatures, and ancillary facilities [57]. The hydrogen was produced and liquified in Australia before being exported to Japan by a ship with 1,250 m³ liquid hydrogen capacity to be unloaded into the spherical storage tank [58]. Figure 18 provides an overview of the facilities at the Kobe terminal.

Figure 18. Overview of the Kobe liquid hydrogen import terminal in Japan [58]

The spatial footprint for the pilot liquid hydrogen import terminal at Kobe is 1 ha (Figure 19). The hydrogen storage capacity is expected to handle approximately 6,500 tonnes per annum (or 25 MW_{H₂}), assuming the tank has a similar throughput factor and process as the OCI ammonia import terminal (see section 3.2.5). The spatial requirement of the Kobe liquid hydrogen terminal amounts to 40 ha/GW (Table 6). The estimated spatial footprint of the Kobe pilot site is significantly larger than that of the NASA site. The Kobe site contains a smaller tank capacity and also includes auxiliary facilities and more empty plot space compared to selected footprint of the NASA facility, which is limited to the plot of the storage tank only. This could potentially be reduced by increasing the Kobe storage tank capacity to that utilised at the NASA facility.

Figure 19. Aerial view and spatial footprint of the Kobe liquid hydrogen import terminal (Google Earth, coordinates: 34°38'27"N 135°14'09"E, data attribution: 4/22/2022) [37]

Table 6. Liquid hydrogen import terminal estimated space and throughput parameters

	Current use	Tank capacity m ³	Through-put kt _{H₂} /yr	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H₂}	Source
NASA liquid hydrogen storage	LH ₂	4,732	12	0.32	6.8	[54]
Kobe import terminal (pilot)	LH ₂	2,500	6.5	1	40	[57]
Selected range			-	-	6.8-40	[54] [57]

Besides storage, for liquid hydrogen to be injected into the gas grid it requires a regasification process and facility. This is expected to require less energy than liquefaction and the liquid hydrogen can be regasified and heated up by heat exchange with seawater or air. The spatial requirements for such a process are considered limited and assumed to fall within the plot space of the LH₂ storage facility.

3.2.5 Hydrogen import – ammonia import and storage

Many of the hydrogen import projects currently planned in the Netherlands are focussed on ammonia as a hydrogen carrier. To estimate the spatial requirement for ammonia import infrastructure, facilities from OCI, Vopak, and the ACE Terminal are analysed.

OCI currently operates the only ammonia import facility in the port of Rotterdam [59]. OCI is expanding this facility, where the first phase of the expansion increased the capacity from 400 ktpa to 1.2 million tpa in 2023. This was achieved through low cost upgrades to the existing terminal infrastructure. The second phase will include a new large-scale ammonia storage tank and a scale-up in jetty infrastructure to increase the throughput capacity of the terminal to 3 million tpa [60]. The second phase received a permit in 2024 for the construction of the new 60,000 tonnes capacity ammonia storage tank [61]. Based on this data, we estimate an average throughput factor of 37, which means that the volume of a terminal can be loaded and unloaded 37 times a year (see also the Appendix). This factor is applied to estimate the throughput of all hydrogen import terminals.

The OCI ammonia facility in the port of Rotterdam covers a spatial footprint of 5.3 ha (Figure 20, left). The spatial footprint excludes the space requirement of a jetty. Figure 20 (right) demonstrates the size

Figure 21. Aerial view and spatial footprint of the Vopak LPG terminal in Vlissingen (Google Earth, coordinates: 51°27'43"N 3°43'02"E, data attribution: 6/6/2023) [37]

Gasunie and Vopak are planning to develop the ACE ammonia import terminal in the Maasvlakte, Rotterdam. Having an ammonia cracker on site for converting the imported ammonia back into hydrogen may be a future consideration for the terminal [64]. The Gasunie Peakshaver site at the Maasvlakte is a short-term LNG storage facility for gasifying LNG at peak times with two large tanks storing 78 million m³ together [65][66]. The plans for the ACE Terminal at the Peakshaver site are outlined in Figure 22 (right). The partners in ACE Terminal also supported the study by Fluor on large-scale ammonia cracking facilities in the port of Rotterdam [67].

The spatial footprint of the ACE Terminal in Rotterdam is determined at 11.4 ha (Figure 22). It was assumed that the facility could store 78 million m³ of natural gas when at normal temperature and pressure. This was translated to LNG to estimate the tank size, leading to a tank capacity of about 68,000 m³ for each of the two tanks. Assuming the same volume in cubic metres of ammonia is stored in those tanks, the estimated ammonia throughput capacity in tonnes amounts to roughly 3 million tonnes per year, which corresponds to 460 ktpa (or 1.8 GW) of hydrogen, using the conversion factors in the Appendix. The spatial requirement, thus, amounts to 6.5 ha/GW_{H2} (Table 7).

Figure 22. Left: aerial view and spatial footprint of the Peakshaver site in Port of Rotterdam (Google Earth, coordinates: 51°56'36"N 4°04'00"E, data attribution: 4/15/2023) [37]; Right: plans for ACE import terminal [68]

Table 7. Ammonia import terminal estimated space and throughput parameters

	Current use	Tank capacity m ³	Throughput kt _{NH₃} /yr	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H₂}	Source
OCI Ammonia Terminal 2023	NH ₃	46,600	1200	5.3	7.7	[60] [62]
OCI Ammonia Terminal future expansion	NH ₃	144,100	3000	5.3	3.1	[60] [62]
Vopak LPG Terminal	LPG	110,000	2500	17.3	12	[49], [63]
ACE terminal	LNG	136,000	3000	11.4	6.5	[66]
Selected range			-	-	3.1-12	[60] [63]

The aerial views of the facilities indicate potential space for capacity expansion and increasing the density of the plot if necessary. The spatial requirements of the three systems analysed were similar, with a range of 3.1 to 12 ha/GW_{H₂} for hydrogen import and storage in the form of green ammonia. There are also other ammonia import facilities planned in the Netherlands, such as the Air Products and Gunvor facility and the VTTI Amplifly facility in Rotterdam. These are not expected to come online before 2026 [69] [70]. To convert the ammonia back to green hydrogen, ammonia cracking facilities will be required, as will be discussed in the next section.

3.2.6 Hydrogen import – ammonia cracking

Imported green ammonia can be converted back to green hydrogen via the ammonia cracking process, where the ammonia synthesis reaction is reversed at high temperatures in a catalytic cracking furnace [71]. There has been large interest in developing ammonia cracking facilities in the port of Rotterdam to enable the import of green hydrogen via ammonia. Several technology providers, such as Topsoe, Duiker, H2SITE, and more, are able to provide ammonia cracking technologies with high TRL levels that can crack ammonia to the required hydrogen purity and pressure [72]. To estimate the spatial requirement for an ammonia cracking facility, the pre-feasibility study by Fluor for a large-scale ammonia cracking plant in the port of Rotterdam and the existing Arroyito heavy water production facility in Argentina were analysed.

The pre-feasibility study by Fluor was commissioned by several large industry actors and released in 2023. In the study, a large central cracking facility is analysed with a hydrogen production capacity of 1 million tons per year from 20,000 tons of imported ammonia per day. The centralised cracker can either be accompanied by multiple different ammonia import and storage locations or by ammonia import and storage at the same location as the cracker. Alternatively, decentralised crackers could potentially be implemented at various ammonia import and storage sites. Cost benefits were expected with the central cracking system with storage and logistics facilities at one location. Potential locations for cracker facilities were not included in the pre-feasibility study. The space requirements, including storage, for 1 million tons of hydrogen production capacity was estimated to be 20-45 ha. Based on this, the spatial requirement of the cracker is 5.3-12 ha/GW_{H₂} (Table 8). It was noted that this estimate is conservative and that the space requirements can be refined when plant locations have been selected [72].

The Arroyito heavy water production plant in Argentina has production capacity of 200 tonnes per year of heavy water using the Monothermal Ammonia-Hydrogen Isotopic exchange method. The facility includes multiple heat exchangers, pressure vessels, compressors, reactors, and distillation columns. The facility contains two ammonia synthesis reactors with a capacity of 2150 tonnes/day each [73].

The Monothermal Ammonia-Hydrogen Isotopic exchange method also includes the use of an ammonia cracking unit(s) [74] [75]. The ammonia cracking unit for the Arroyito facility was provided by Topsoe using their H2Retake technology. This is currently Topsoe’s largest ammonia cracking plant with a capacity of 2400 tonnes/day in each of the two parallel lines [76].

The spatial footprint of the heavy water production plant, including the ammonia cracker, is estimated at 8.4 ha (Figure 23). It was assumed that the capacity of 4800 tonnes/day relates to ammonia input into the cracking unit and not hydrogen produced from the cracking process. This scale corresponds with a hydrogen production capacity of 1.0 GW_{H2}. Not the whole plant area can be attributed to the cracking facility. The Monothermal Ammonia-Hydrogen Isotopic exchange method requires the use of multiple different equipment units, including isotopic exchange units, ammonia synthesis units, catalyst stripping units, purification units, ammonia cracking units, and more [74] [75]. For this analysis, we assume that roughly one third of the space of the plot is allocated to the ammonia cracker unit, while the other space is required for the heavy water production and ammonia synthesis related equipment (each with their auxiliary processes). The spatial requirement of the cracker thus amounts to 2.8 ha/GW_{H2} (Table 8).

Figure 23. Aerial view and spatial footprint of the Arroyito heavy water production plant in Argentina (Google Earth, coordinates: 39°06'02"S 68°35'53"W, data attribution: 11/13/2022) [37]

Table 8. Ammonia cracking estimated space and throughput parameters

	H ₂ production capacity kt _{H2} /day	Throughput kt _{NH3} /day	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H2}	Source
Fluor study	3	20	20-45	5.3-12	[72]
Arroyito facility	0.7	4.8	2.8	2.8	[73] [76]
Selected range		-	-	2.8-12	[72] [76]

The spatial requirement from the Fluor study gave insight into ammonia cracking plans for the Netherlands, while the Arroyito facility gave insight into a reference ammonia cracking unit. There are also other ammonia cracking facilities planned in Europe, like the Air Liquide plans for an industrial

scale green ammonia cracking pilot plant in the port of Antwerp. The project plans to be operational in 2024 [77].

3.2.7 Hydrogen import – methanol import and storage

Hydrogen can also be transported in methanol as carrier [50]. It should be noted that the role of green methanol may go beyond the role of solely a hydrogen carrier, as methanol is currently mainly used in the chemical industry and directly as transport fuel, and conversion back to hydrogen may not be necessary. The methanol market may grow further as green methanol is largely discussed in the context of bunkering for fuelling ships, for example, the OCI Global bunkering of the world’s first green methanol fuelled container vessel in the port of Rotterdam [78]. For comparative reasons, methanol, as a liquid with a relatively high volumetric energy density, is included as a storage option for hydrogen. Methanol can already be stored at various facilities in the port of Rotterdam, such as the facilities at ETT, Vopak, and more [79].

The spatial requirement for methanol import is based theoretically on oil import and storage. A section of the Euro Tank Terminal (ETT) facility owned by VTTI in the port of Rotterdam was used as a baseline for understanding the spatial requirements for methanol import, as well as for liquid organic hydrogen carrier (LOHC) import (discussed in 3.2.8). The ETT facility handles products like ethanol, methanol, gasoil, and jet fuel in 42 tanks [80]. A plot section with 8 tanks from the ETT facility close to the OCI ammonia import terminal was utilised to estimate the spatial requirement for methanol storage and import infrastructure. The spatial footprint for the ETT import facility in the port of Rotterdam amounts to 5.1 ha (Figure 24, left). Based on plot drawings in the OCI permitting documentation that also provides information on the neighbouring ETT facility, the 8 tanks of various sizes have a combined capacity of 278,000 m³ (Figure 24, right).

Figure 24. Left: aerial view and spatial footprint of an ETT oil import facility in port of Rotterdam (Google Earth, coordinates 51°55'37"N 4°11'38"E, data attribution: 6/6/2023) [37]; Right: section of plot plans from OCI ammonia import terminal expansion permitting documents that provides information on the ETT terminal [62]

Such a volumetric capacity can contain around 220 kt of methanol or, if the methanol is reformed with steam and heat, around 42 kt of hydrogen. This corresponds to a volumetric hydrogen storage density of 150 kg/m³. The hydrogen throughput per year for the facility is estimated at approximately 1500 ktpa by applying the same factor as used with the throughput of the OCI ammonia terminal. The specific footprint amounts to 0.9 ha/GW_{H₂}. This spatial requirement is shown to be smaller than that

for ammonia and liquid hydrogen, but does not include space for the reformer unit. Hydrogen can be produced from methanol using steam reforming, autothermal reforming, partial oxidation or methanol decomposition [81]. There are no known large-scale methanol steam reformers, but there are some smaller reactors available on the market and under development [82] [83]. For large-scale reformers, we expect the spatial footprint to be similar to that of steam methane reformers or autothermal methane reformers (see 3.2.2). It should also be noted that the ETT facility used to estimate the spatial requirement for methanol is more densely packed than the previously analysed facilities for ammonia and liquid hydrogen.

3.2.8 Hydrogen import – LOHC import and storage

Hydrogen can also be stored and transported in an LOHC [50]. Methylcyclohexane and toluene (MCH-TOL) and dibenzyl-toluene and perhydro-dibenzyl-toluene (DBT-PDBT) are considered, as these are some of the more well-investigated LOHC's [15]. The volumetric hydrogen storage density for MCH-TOL is around 47 kg/m³ and 64 kg/m³ for DBT-PDBT. The hydrogen is released from the MCH and PDBT via a dehydrogenation process to produce toluene and DBT using catalysts, like platinum or palladium, and high temperature heat [15] (see also section 3.2.9).

The spatial requirement estimate of LOHC import and storage is also based on the capacity and plot size of a section of the ETT import terminal facility in the port of Rotterdam, as these LOHC's are liquids and comparable to other oil products. The throughput in hydrogen equivalents is determined at 480 ktpa and 650 ktpa hydrogen, which results in a specific spatial footprint of 5.6 and 4.0 ha/GW_{H₂} for MCH and PDBT, respectively, using the conversion factors in the Appendix This spatial requirement includes the assumption that for both LOHC's the storage need is doubled to account for the space required for the hydrogenated carrier as well as the space required for the dehydrogenated LOHC. The spatial footprint does not include the space required for dehydrogenation facilities. The spatial requirement results are presented Table 9.

Figure 25. Aerial view and spatial footprint of the dehydrogenation facility in Kawasaki (Google Earth, coordinates: 35°30'53"N 139°44'43"E, data attribution: 03/09/2022) [37] [87]

Multiple LOHC import facilities have been planned in the Netherlands. Evos, Hydrogenious, and Port of Amsterdam are planning to develop large-scale LOHC import facilities with a capacity of 100-500 tonnes of hydrogen released per day. The facility will include storage, dehydrogenation, and handling. It is planned for the plant to be operational by 2028 and have potential for further expansion. Evos

storage terminals in Amsterdam will be repurposed with minor modifications for the benzyl-toluene LOHC, which can be handled at ambient temperature and pressure and be reused many times to bind with hydrogen after the dehydrogenation process [84]. A joint feasibility study is also planned by the Port of Rotterdam, Koole Terminals, Chiyoda Corporation, and Mitsubishi Corporation for large-scale hydrogen import to a Koole terminal in the port of Rotterdam using the SPERA Hydrogen Technology by Chiyoda for transport, storage, and dehydrogenation of LOHCs. The plans involve MCH as the carrier and the SPERA Hydrogen technology for the dehydrogenation process for import of 100-200 ktpa hydrogen in 2025 (with potential for further expansion) [85]. The SPERA Hydrogen technology has undergone a demonstration project with hydrogenation taking place in Brunei and dehydrogenation taking place in Kawasaki [86].

Via such a dehydrogenation process, the hydrogen is released from the LOHCs. The dehydrogenation demonstration project took place in 2020 via the Global Hydrogen Supply Chain Demonstration Project by Chiyoda, Mitsubishi, Mitsui & Co., and Nippon Yusen Kabushiki Kaisha. The project included a hydrogenation plant in Brunei and a dehydrogenation plant in Kawasaki, Japan. Hydrogen in the form of liquid MCH at ambient temperature and pressure was shipped from Brunei to Kawasaki, where hydrogen gas was extracted from the carrier using the SPERA Hydrogen Technology by Chiyoda.

Table 9. Methanol and LOHC import terminal estimated space and throughput parameters

	Current use	Tank capacity m ³	Through-put kt _{H₂} /yr	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _{H₂}	Source
Methanol	oil	278,000	1500	5.1	0.9	[62]
MCH	oil	278,000	480	5.1	5.6	[15] [62]
PDBT	oil	278,000	650	5.1	4.0	[15] [62]
<i>Kawasaki dehydrogenation demonstration</i>	<i>MCH dehydrogenation</i>		0.21	0.16	200	[88]
Selected range						
Methanol			-	-	0.9	[15] [62]
LOHC			-	-	4.0-5.6	[15] [62]

The hydrogen production capacity of the dehydrogenation facility was 210 tpa in 2020. The project was in operation from January to December 2020 [88]. The demonstration dehydrogenation facility in Kawasaki was used to estimate the spatial footprint of LOHC dehydrogenation plants. The facility includes a dehydrogenation unit, MCH/toluene storage tanks, a loading/unloading facility, and a control building. The LOHC was transported to the dehydrogenation facility via a ISO tank container trailer from the Kawasaki Port Container Terminal and the hydrogen produced was used in an adjacent power plant [87]. The spatial footprint of the dehydrogenation facility in Kawasaki was estimated to be 0.16 ha (Figure 25), which results in a specific footprint of 200 ha/GW_{H₂} (Table 9). This specific footprint is substantially larger than that of other systems analysed due to the comparatively lower capacity of the demonstration plant. As earlier mentioned, the area use for the dehydrogenation unit is not included in the specific footprint range of the LOHC storage facility due to the small-scale demonstration nature of the facility.

3.2.9 Hydrogen transport infrastructure – pipelines

For the hydrogen pipeline infrastructure spatial footprint the assumptions from the II3050 and the PEH studies were followed [4] [9]. The hydrogen transport network will consist of a high pressure network (HTL), medium pressure network (RTL), and distribution networks. The hydrogen HTL pipelines will be

placed in existing national pipeline corridors together with other, mainly natural gas pipelines. These pipeline corridors have a usual width of 70 meters [4]. The spatial footprint is therefore determined by the cumulative length of the HTL pipelines and the 70 meter width. The aboveground space of the pipeline corridors cannot be built on, or cannot be built on completely, but the space can often be used for agricultural purposes [4].

The RTL pipelines are not usually placed in a pipeline corridor. For hydrogen RTL pipelines, regulations prescribe that it is required to reserve 5 metres of space on either side of the pipeline [4] [9]. For natural gas RTL pipelines the required space reservation is 4 metres on each side [4] [9]. The hydrogen RTL pipelines therefore require a total space reservation of at least 10 metres, 2 of which are at least additional compared to existing natural gas pipelines in case of repurposing. Additional safety constraints may apply to the space used in the surrounding area of the corridors. This safety area is excluded from our analysis.

For the distribution networks, the I13050 and PEH do not give estimates for the spatial footprint. Netbeheer Nederland expects the distribution networks to claim a relatively small amount of additional space as the pipelines will mostly be placed under roads and sidewalks, meaning that the space can be used for multiple purposes [89].

Auxiliary equipment, such as pressure regulators, metering installations, purification units, and injection and connection stations, is also required for a proper functioning of the hydrogen network. This equipment is typically installed connected to or in close proximity of the pipelines and likely mainly occupies space within the corridors. In the I13050 study, the potential need for a few new compressor stations is mentioned, but the spatial footprint is fairly limited (<0.01 km², see also section 2.1.4 Hydrogen infrastructure in the I13050 scenarios). For RTL and distribution networks, some additional space may be required to accommodate for these installations, but data on how this might evolve is scarce. It is expected that the impact on the total space requirement is limited and does not ascribe additional space for this equipment in this analysis.

3.2.10 Hydrogen underground storage facilities – salt caverns

Salt caverns serve as underground storage reservoirs for hydrogen, comparable to natural gas storage. These caverns are created through solution mining, where fresh water is injected into bedded salt formations or salt pillars in the subsurface. The process dissolves the salt, forming large cavities capable of storing hydrogen. Salt caverns are known for their impermeability, making them ideal containers for fluids and gases. The caverns are typically created at depths exceeding 300 meters and can have geometric volumes ranging from 100,000 m³ to several million m³, although those specifically for gas storage rarely exceed 1,000,000 m³ [90]. Once formed, the caverns are filled with brine during solution mining operations, ensuring structural integrity. Notably, salt cavern storage does not significantly impact the quality of stored hydrogen, meeting purity requirements of over 99% without extensive cleaning [90].

Currently, four storage facilities for pure hydrogen in salt caverns are operational worldwide, primarily supporting the chemical industry's continuous manufacturing processes [90]. Practical experience demonstrates the long-term safety and viability of hydrogen storage in salt caverns. However, challenges arise when transitioning to fast-cycle operations to balance supply and demand during extreme weather conditions. These challenges, including maintaining the integrity of well materials and interfaces, lower the TRL from mature to lower levels. Pilot and demonstration projects in Europe aim to raise the TRL to 7, addressing these operational challenges [91]. The infrastructure of a salt cavern storage facility includes wells for injection into and withdrawal from the caverns, pipelines connecting the wells to surface gas processing facilities, and electrical equipment. Surface equipment

encompasses a control system, injection motors, compressors, expanders, and electricity generators. The facility connects to the hydrogen transportation network, enabling the flow of hydrogen between production facilities and consumption points. The spatial parameters of the natural gas salt cavern storage Zuidwending, in the Netherlands, is used for this analysis. These caverns can also be used for hydrogen and possess a storage capacity of 6 kton hydrogen per salt cavern [91]. In our analysis of the Zuidwending salt cavern, the high side of the range, 63 ha/TWh_{H₂}, is determined by the area required for licensing and permitting of the salt cavern [92]. While the licensed area may be extensive, it can still serve other purposes like agriculture, housing, or urban development. Only a portion of the licensed area is actively utilized on the surface for the storage facility's operations. The estimated actual surface area utilized for the technology's infrastructure determines our low side of the range, i.e. 10 ha/TWh_{H₂} (see Figure 26 and Table 10).

Figure 26. Spatial requirements for Zuidwending salt cavern A: Infrastructure (coordinates: 53°05'02"N 6°56'06"E) and B: Licensing [37] [92]

3.2.11 Hydrogen underground storage facilities – gas fields

Hydrogen can also be stored in depleted natural gas fields. These fields, which previously held natural gas, consist of porous reservoir rocks sealed by impermeable layers, such as clay or salt, preventing gas migration upward through the subsurface [90]. This setup, along with an underlying aquifer in some cases, can provide an effective hydrogen storage reservoir.

In terms of technology readiness, gas field storage for hydrogen has reached a relatively high level. While challenges remain, such as ensuring the integrity of wellbore materials and interfaces due to frequent and cyclic injection and withdrawal, practical experience has demonstrated the feasibility of storing hydrogen in depleted gas fields. Pilot and demonstration projects are underway to further advance the technology and address remaining questions regarding its environmental and economic implications [93]. The system components of a scaled-up gas field storage plant include both underground and surface-level elements. Underground, multiple wells are connected to a control system, which manages the injection and withdrawal of hydrogen. These wells are linked underground to the same gas field, forming an interconnected network. Surface equipment consists of a control system, injection motors, compressors, expanders, and electricity generators. Additionally, there exists a connection to the hydrogen network facilitating the transportation of hydrogen between production and consumption points. Similar to the salt cavern storage, the high end of the range is determined by the area required for licensing and permitting gas field use, while the low end covers only the actual surface area utilized for the technology's infrastructure (see Figure 27 and Table 10). Notably, the licensed area can be extensive, but still serve other purposes like agriculture, housing, or urban development. If and how the licensed area requirements and/or limited multi-use of space may differ

for underground hydrogen storage is yet unknown. The specific footprints for hydrogen storage in depleted gas fields are based on the spatial utilization of the natural gas storage in Gas Storage Bergermeer in Alkmaar, Netherlands, which contains a potential storage capacity of 387 kton of hydrogen and results in a spatial footprint ranging from 1.5 to 150 ha/TWh_{H2} [94] [95] [96].

Figure 27. Spatial requirements for Bergermeer gas field A: infrastructure (coordinates: 52°35'55.84"N 4°44'54.45"E) and B: Licensing [37] [95]

Table 10. Underground hydrogen storage space and storage parameters

	Storage capacity TWh _{H2}	Plot size - only well and facilities ha	Plot size – licensing and permit ha	Specific footprint ha/TWh _{H2}	Source
Salt caverns – Zuidwending	2	19.7	125	10-63	[91] [92] [37]
Gas fields – Bergermeer	13	19.3	1945	1.5-150	[94] [37] [95]
Selected range				1.5-150	[94] [37] [95]

The II3050 study reports a spatial footprint of 8 TWh/km₂ or 12.5 ha/TWh of aboveground area usage for underground hydrogen storage [4]. Such a figure corresponds to the lower part of our determined bandwidth (Table 10).

3.2.12 Hydrogen demand facilities – hydrogen refuelling stations

The hydrogen refuelling stations (HRS) network is rapidly expanding worldwide, with Asia leading with 275 HRS, followed by Europe with approximately 200 HRS, and North America with 75 HRS. In Europe, Germany boasts nearly 100 HRS strategically located along national highways and trans-European corridors [97]. This growth reflects a global effort to establish a reliable infrastructure to support hydrogen-powered vehicles. Germany and the Benelux are forefront in Europe, and have built a HRS network in recent years. Small stations, capable of throughput up to 200 kg H₂/day, and medium stations, with throughput up to 500 kg H₂/day, have been constructed to facilitate the initial ramp-up of public HRS. These stations typically offer refuelling at 700 bar for passenger vehicles and light-duty vehicles, and at 350 bar for buses [97].

The readiness level of HRS technologies can be assessed based on four key criteria: supply chain readiness, vehicle storage system readiness, HRS readiness, and the maturity of standards for HRS.

Technologies like 350 bar and 700 bar compressed gaseous hydrogen (CGH₂) are relatively mature and are already in use for buses and medium-duty vehicles, with numerous pilot and demonstration projects underway across Europe [98]. The average spatial footprint of ten HRS installations in the BENELUX region, like the Shell Amsterdam Westpoort HRS and the Total Energies Utrecht HRS, amounts to 0.3 ha, covering a range of 0.14-0.66 ha (Table 12). However, it is worth noting that these stations are not yet being utilized in the most spatially efficient manner. Many of these stations are not exclusively dedicated to hydrogen and are often developed in areas without known spatial constraints. The capacity of these refuelling stations is also not typically reported. The current low demand for hydrogen does not yet justify full capacity utilization, highlighting the need for improvement in other components of the readiness level, particularly in the supply chain for both hydrogen supply and demand. The current low demand is attributed to the small market share of hydrogen vehicles. Figure 29 also shows aerial snapshots of some of these facilities for better visualization.

Hydrogen refuelling stations consist of various systems and subsystems, which vary depending on the type of station. For example, stations utilizing 350-700 bar compressed gaseous hydrogen (CGH₂) technology, commonly found in current demonstration projects in BENELUX, incorporate medium and high-pressure storage tanks, trailer swaps, compressors, and control units [97]. Similarly, stations employing subcooled liquid hydrogen (sLH₂) and cryo-compressed hydrogen (CCH₂) technologies utilize similar components tailored to their specific low-temperature and high-pressure requirements. However, these latter two technologies are still in development and not yet fully ready for pilot projects [97]. H₂ Mobility [97] has assessed the spatial footprint of such systems, analysing the space needed to deploy these refuelling station components at an operational level, with results detailed in Table 11 and Figure 28. It is important to note, however, that this analysis only considers new, dedicated hydrogen facilities. Many hydrogen refuelling stations are expected to be integrated in existing gas stations, which may not significantly impact their total spatial footprints.

Table 11. Hydrogen refuelling station space and capacity parameters

Type of refuelling station	Pressure (bar)	Equipment Spatial Footprint (ha)	Capacity (kg / day)	Source
Small Station	350-700	0.01-0.03	200	[97]
Medium Station	350-700	0.02-0.04	500	[97]
Large Station	350-700	0.03-0.08	1000	[97]

Figure 28. Large 350-700 bar compressed gaseous hydrogen equipment and system overview [97]

Figure 29 – Hydrogen refuelling stations spatial snapshots. A: Shell - Amsterdam Westpoort (coordinates: 52°23'46.23"N 4°48'2.64"E); B: Total Energies - Utrecht (coordinates: 52° 6'59.48"N 5° 1'52.50"E); C: H2Point - Rosendaal (coordinates: 51°33'27.72"N 4°27'11.69"E) [37]

Although unknown, it seems unlikely that operational refuelling stations, considering the limited market share of hydrogen-fuelled vehicles, will exceed the medium size capacity (500 kgH₂/day). Therefore, the lowest area usage is correlated to a capacity of 200 kgH₂/day, while the high end of the range is related to a capacity of 500 kgH₂/day. This results in specific spatial footprints of 58-108 ha/TWh_{H₂}/year, as presented in Table 12.

Table 12. Hydrogen refuelling stations estimated specific spatial footprint based on existing refuelling stations

	Spatial footprint ha	Assumed capacity kg H ₂ /day	Specific footprint ha/TWh _{H₂} /year	Source
Minimum based on 10 operational refuelling stations	0.140	200	58	[37] [97] [98]
Maximum based on 10 operational refuelling stations	0.660	500	108	[37] [97] [98]
Selected range			58-108	[37] [97] [98]

3.2.13 Hydrogen demand facilities – hydrogen combined cycle gas turbines

Hydrogen combined cycle gas turbine (CCGT) power plants make use of a combination of gas turbines and steam turbines, thereby achieving a higher efficiency (up to 60%) than gas turbine power plants. There are no hydrogen-fired CCGT's in operation yet in the Netherlands, although the conversion of some plants is being considered (e.g. the Enecogen plant [99]). For the spatial requirement assessment we have looked at several existing natural gas based CCGT's in the Netherlands. The spatial footprint of hydrogen CCGT's is expected to be similar to the current natural gas-fired plants, especially if existing plants are converted to hydrogen-fired plants. These existing natural gas-fired plants differ greatly in both capacity and in plot size (see Table 13). The plot size is affected by e.g. the type and age of the power plant and the space available in the region of the power plant. The perimeter used to determine the plot size also influences the overall spatial footprint estimate. Therefore we have used multiple plants to determine a bandwidth of the spatial footprint for hydrogen CCGT's (see also Figure 30).

Table 13. Dutch natural gas-fired CCGT spatial footprints.

	Plant capacity (MW _e)	Plot size (ha)	Spatial footprint (ha/GW _e)	Source
Enecogen	870	4.0	5	[100] [37]
Engie Maxima Power Plant	880	3.6	4	[101] [37]
Engie Eemscentrale	1931	11.7	6	[102] [37]
Uniper ¹ Rotterdam Capelle	264	2.6	10	[103] [37]
Uniper ¹ Den Haag	107	2.8	26	[103] [37]
Uniper ¹ Leiden	85	1.1	13	[103] [37]
RWE Moerdijk	426	9.5	22	[104] [37]
RWE Magnum Power plant	1410	5.9	4	[105] [37]
RWE Claus C Power Plant	1304	8.3	6	[106] [37]
Selected range			4-26	

¹The Uniper plants also deliver heat to district heating networks in the cities where the plants are located

Figure 30. CCGT spatial snapshots. A: Engie Maxima Power Plant (coordinates: 52°34'35"N 5°31'45"E), B: Engie Eemscentrale (coordinates: 53°26'07"N 6°52'43"E), C: RWE Moerdijk (coordinates: 51°41'07"N 4°34'44"E) [37].

3.2.14 Hydrogen demand facilities – hydrogen gas turbines

There are also no hydrogen-fired gas turbine (GT) power plants in the Netherlands. We therefore also base spatial footprint estimates on existing natural gas-fired gas turbines. Over the years, most natural gas-fired turbines have been replaced by the more efficient CCGT's. Therefore not many active GT's remain in the Netherlands. GT's are also often located at the same site as CCGT's, complicating the determination of a specific spatial footprint for these GT's.

Table 14. Natural gas-fired GT spatial footprints.

	Plant capacity MW _e	Plot size ha	Specific footprint ha/GW _e	Source
Vattenfall IJmond 1	144	0.7	5	[107] [37]
Engie Zwijndrecht	58	0.9	15	[108] [37]
Selected range			5-15	

For the spatial footprint estimates we compare two GT's, one in the Netherlands and one in Belgium (see Table 14 and Figure 31). The Vattenfall IJmond 1 plant is located on the Tata Steel IJmuiden site and primarily uses waste gases from the steel production site as a fuel [107]. The Engie plant in Zwijndrecht is a CHP unit on the former site of synthetic rubber producer Arlanxco [108]. The Engie plant has a smaller capacity, but takes up slightly more space. The specific spatial footprint of the Engie plant is therefore larger than the Vattenfall IJmond 1 plant. In general the GT's are smaller in capacity than CCGT's. Because the GT plants are also more compact, the specific spatial footprint is similar to and falls within the range of that of the CCGT's.

In the II3050 and PEH analyses, a specific spatial footprint for gas turbines (it is not specified whether these are CCGT or GT) of $21.3 \text{ GW}_e / \text{km}^2$ or $4.7 \text{ ha} / \text{GW}_e$ is reported [9] [4].

Figure 31. GT spatial snapshots A: Vattenfall IJmond GT plant (coordinates: $52^{\circ}28'30''\text{N } 4^{\circ}36'17''\text{E}$), B: Engie Zwijndrecht GT plant (coordinates: $51^{\circ}14'12''\text{N } 4^{\circ}20'08''\text{E}$) [37].

3.3 Overview of subsystems and their spatial requirements

The findings related to the spatial requirements per subsystem are summarised in Table 15. The extremes of the ranges have been used for the calculation of the low and high spatial requirements in Chapter 4. For onshore electrolysis, only the large-scale electrolysis range is used for the analysis and the range for smaller-scale systems is excluded. The SMR range is used for the SMR/ATR systems. For hydrogen import, a value of 5.9 ha/GW_{H2} is used as the optimistic value, which corresponds to a methanol import terminal with a methanol SMR. The lower bound of the other import options is similar to this value. The upper bound of a liquid hydrogen terminal is used as the most conservative value of area usage for hydrogen import. The range found for depleted gas fields is used for underground hydrogen storage, and, thus, also covers the range of hydrogen storage in salt caverns.

Table 15. Overview of subsystems and the bandwidth in their spatial footprint based on the analysis in the previous paragraphs. For some subsystems, the amount of data is limited and the spatial footprint estimate is only a single value instead of a bandwidth. Values used for the spatial area analysis of the I13050 scenarios are depicted in bold.

Category	Subsystem ¹	Unit	Spatial footprint	Source ²
Hydrogen production	Onshore large-scale electrolyser	ha/GW _e	10-44	[17] [20]
	Onshore small-scale electrolyser	ha/GW _e	4.5-208	[21] [29]
	Offshore electrolyser	ha/GW _e	0.6-10	[30] [33]
	Steam methane reformer (SMR)	ha/GW _{H2}	5-21	[36]
	Autothermal reformer (ATR)	ha/GW _{H2}	14	[41]
	Biomass gasification	ha/GW _{H2}	39-332	[44] [47]
Hydrogen import	Ammonia import and storage	ha/GW _{H2}	3.1-12	[60] [63]
	Ammonia cracker	ha/GW _{H2}	2.8-12	[72] [76]
	Liquid hydrogen import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	6.8-40	[54] [57]
	Methanol import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	0.9	[62]
	Methanol reformer	ha/GW _{H2}	5-21	[36]
	LOHC import terminal	ha/GW _{H2}	4.0-5.6	[15] [62]
	LOHC dehydrogenation	ha/GW _{H2}	Only demo, excl. from analysis	[88]
Hydrogen storage	Salt caverns	ha/TWh	10-63	[91] [92]
	Depleted gas fields	ha/TWh	1.5-150	[93] [94]
Hydrogen demand	Refuelling stations	ha/TWh _{H2} /year	58-108	[97] [98]
	Hydrogen CCGT	ha/GW _e	4-26	[101] [103]
	Hydrogen GT	ha/GW _e	5-15	[107] [108]

¹ Ranges of the subsystems that are represented in bold are used to determine the total area requirements in the spatial analysis. ² For most existing facilities, Google Earth was also used to estimate the spatial footprint [37].

4. Spatial requirement contours of hydrogen projects

In this chapter, the scenario data from Chapter 2 and the spatial footprints per subsystem from Chapter 3 are combined for an assessment of the total space requirement for the hydrogen system. A comparison is also made with estimates for the I13050 and PEH, where these are available for a subsystem.

4.1 Total spatial requirements for each of the scenarios

The total spatial requirement varies per scenario (see Figure 32). The total spatial requirement estimates are 80-101 km² in 2030, 85-219 km² in 2040 and 99-280 km² in 2050, or 3-24 km² in 2030, 7-92 km² in 2040 and 11-155 km² in 2050 when the pipeline subsystem is excluded. The high estimates are especially significant, for comparison, the land area of the island Texel equals around 160 km². It is however limited if compared to the area that is required to harvest the energy. In the I13050 study, it is indicated that offshore wind may require 3,800-7,200 km², onshore wind 1,250-2,500 km², and solar parks 350-580 km². Arguably, a substantial share of these areas can be ascribed to the hydrogen system, for instance to supply electricity for electrolysis. These systems are, however, excluded from our scope. The National Leadership scenario requires the least space (low estimate) and the International Trade scenario requires the most space (high estimate). The International Trade scenario requires the most space for both the low and high estimates while the differences between the other three scenarios are limited. The low and high estimates for each scenario result from the bandwidths in spatial footprint, which is described for (nearly) all of the subsystems. Only for the pipeline subsystem, an exception is made and no range is described, as we follow the same reasoning and assumptions as the I13050 scenarios. The area for the pipeline subsystem mainly varies among the different scenarios and only slightly in the low and high cases for 2040 as explained below.

The largest space requirement is for the hydrogen pipeline network, from 77 km² in 2030 up to 88-125 km² in 2050. The lower bound for the 2040 estimates are based on the 2030 estimates and the upper bound on the 2050 estimates. The estimated spatial footprint for 2040 will lie somewhere in between the estimates of these two years, depending on how much of the network as planned for 2050 has already been developed by 2040. The majority, currently estimated at 67-85% [109], of the pipeline network is repurposed from the natural gas grid [3]. Even new high pressure pipelines (HTL) are placed in existing pipeline corridors and hence do not claim new space [3]. The regional hydrogen pipelines (RTL) require slightly more specific space than natural gas RTL pipelines due to safety distances, even if they are placed in the same location as the existing natural gas pipelines (see 3.2.9). Overall, the area ascribed to the hydrogen RTL network is, however, lower than that of the current natural gas RTL grid. For the regional distribution networks, the amount of spatial use will largely depend on the percentage of repurposed pipelines. In the beginning there will be new pipelines needed to make it possible to separate part of the existing grid from the part which will stay in use for natural gas or biomethane. Unlike Gasunie, regional distributors have mostly only one pipeline in a street and this makes repurposing in the start more challenging. The grid operators expect that no significant amount of additional (aboveground) space will be required for the distribution network as it will replace the existing natural gas network and, like the existing natural gas network, will be placed below roads and sidewalks [89]. Because the percentage of repurposing and, thus, the length of required pipelines for the distribution network is more uncertain, no estimate of the spatial footprint has been made. Our spatial footprint estimate for the hydrogen network is significantly higher than that in the I13050, which only refers to a small additional footprint for new RTL pipelines of <5 km² in the European Integration

scenario and <7 km² in the International Trade scenario [4], while we consider space use for both new and repurposed pipeline infrastructure.

The estimated spatial requirement for hydrogen storage in salt caverns and depleted gas fields differs significantly between the lower and upper bound of the estimates. This is caused by the wide range in spatial requirement per field, with the lower end only being the well and associated facilities and the upper bound being based on the licensing and permits space required (see 3.2.10 and 3.2.11). In the case of the licensing and permitting space, it is also expected that a large part of the space can be used for multiple purposes (e.g., as agricultural land). Underground hydrogen storage in depleted gas fields in the Netherlands is, however, new and may lead to new perceptions of safety contours, possibly extending the licensed area requirements and/or limit multi-use space. Our analysis indicates that the spatial requirement increases from 0.01-10.8 km² in 2030 up to 0.07-46.6 km² in 2040 and 0.1-89 km² in 2050. The range is substantially larger than the estimate in the I13050 study, which reports a spatial footprint of 1.7-3.6 km² in 2050 [4]. The difference is explained by the narrower range of the specific spatial footprint used in the I13050 study, which only considers aboveground facilities (see 3.2.10 and 3.2.11), while our highest estimate covers the total licensed area.

Total spatial area requirement of the hydrogen system incl. repurposed space and multi-use space

Figure 32. Bandwidth estimates of total spatial requirement for the hydrogen subsystems included in the analysis. A large part of the space used can be repurposed space or space that can be used for multiple purposes e.g. aboveground space for pipelines and hydrogen storage. Low and high estimates are based on the low and high spatial footprint estimates per subsystem.

The next largest space requirement is from hydrogen refuelling tank stations. Based on the scenario data, the amount of tank stations increases from 300-3200 in 2030 to 950-9600 in 2040 and 930-13000 in 2050, compared to 4131 tank stations (conventional fuels) in the Netherlands in 2023 [110]. The required amount of hydrogen tank stations corresponds with a spatial area requirement of 1-8 km² in 2030, 3-25 km² in 2040 and 3-35 km² in 2050. Besides the range that is determined by the different scenarios, the amount of stations required also depends on the capacity of each station. The spatial

footprint of the refuelling stations, which is applied in the calculation, is based on an average capacity of 200-500 kgH₂/day. The amount of stations and the space use can be higher or lower if the hydrogen stations contain a different capacity or are integrated with existing (conventional) refuelling stations. Integration with and repurposing of existing refuelling stations also reduces the amount of new space required compared to the current situation.

The spatial area required for hydrogen import terminals varies greatly depending on the import method (liquid hydrogen, ammonia, LOHC, methanol, or another hydrogen carrier or derivative). The I13050 scenarios do not clearly state the hydrogen import carriers used. In this assessment, we use the full range of the specific spatial footprint based on different transport media. The low side of the estimate is based on the import via methanol including a steam methanol reformer, the high side on the most conservative estimate for liquid hydrogen import. The same import routes are used for the peak terminals, but with a slightly adapted approach. The difference between the baseload terminals and peak terminals is that the area requirements of the baseload terminal are based on the capacity to match an average yearly throughput, while the area requirements of the peak terminals are based on only the required storage capacity for the peak supply of hydrogen during several days in the year. As the range reflects the lower and upper bound of the estimated spatial footprints, it is expected that other import media (e.g. ammonia import and cracking) will fall within this bandwidth.

The result is a relatively large difference between the low estimates and the high estimates: 0.3-3.6 km² for 2030, 1.1-9.9 km² in 2040 and 1.9-20.6 km² in 2050. The largest space is required for the International Trade scenario. As illustrated in Figure 33, the peak load import terminals are also a significant contributor to the spatial footprint of the hydrogen import terminals. These results indicate that the choice for a specific hydrogen import method implies a substantial effect on the spatial area requirements. Consequently, at locations where space is limited a different choice may be made on how to import hydrogen than at locations where space constraint are a less severe limitation.

The PEH appendices mention 20 ha of space use in the maximum case in each of the four large ports (Rotterdam, Amsterdam, Eemshaven and Zeeland) for new gas import terminals, based on the spatial footprint of the Gate terminal [9]. It is not clear whether the gas import is meant for LNG or could also refer to hydrogen import terminals. The maximum of 80 hectare (0.8 km²) of space required for import terminals aligns well with the lower bound of our estimate for 2050 (which assumes methanol import, not a gaseous carrier), but is far lower than our upper bound estimates for 2050 (which assumes liquid hydrogen imports).

Electrolysers are also likely to take up significant space (Figure 34). Based on the scenarios, the electrolysers have been split in onshore electrolysers and offshore electrolysers. Their installed capacities in 2050 vary between 10-25 GW_e and 0¹-16.5 GW_e, respectively. Onshore area requirement amounts to 0.3-3.3 km² in 2030, 0.8-7.3 km² in 2040 and 1-11 km² in 2050. In the I13050 study, an area requirement of 3-8 km² is reported for onshore electrolysers in 2050 [4], corresponding relatively well to our estimates.

Offshore space requirement is lower, in part thanks to more efficient space use (see section 3.2.1.3). Offshore platform and/or island area required adds 0.004-0.2 km² in 2030, 0.03-0.9 km² in 2040 and 0.05-2 km² in 2050 (excluding the scenarios in which no offshore capacity is projected¹). The I13050 study does not estimate the spatial footprint of offshore electrolysers. We should note here that the electrolysers consume substantial amounts of electricity, which should likely be supplied by renewable electricity generators such as on- and offshore wind and solar parks. As an example, if we assume that

¹ The National Drivers and European Integration scenarios do not include offshore electrolysis.

offshore wind requires roughly 1 km² for 10 MW_e capacity, a one-to-one (GW_e/GW_e) connection with an electrolyser plant requires an additional 100 km² per GW_e of installed electrolyser capacity. As electricity supply falls out of the scope of our study, these area requirements have not been assessed.

Spatial requirement hydrogen import terminals

Figure 33. Bandwidth estimates of spatial requirement for hydrogen import terminals. Low and high estimates are based on the low and high spatial footprint estimates (methanol and liquid hydrogen respectively).

The spatial area required for SMR decreases from 0.3-1.4 km² in 2030 to 0.1-0.9 km² in 2040, after which it increases again to a maximum of almost 2 km² in the high estimate for 2050 for the European Integration scenario. In the other scenarios the spatial claim for 2050 either is the same as in 2040 (NAT) or reduces compared to 2040 (DEC and INT). The fluctuation follows the fluctuation in installed capacity according to the scenario data. As there is already some SMR/ATR capacity installed now, it can be expected that not all of the area required is an additional space claim. Note that the scenarios assume all SMR will be equipped with CCS from 2030 on, but that the space required for the transport and storage of CO₂ is not within the scope of this analysis.

Biomass gasification requires a relatively large amount of space compared to the production capacity, due to the required space for biomass handling and storage. The spatial requirement estimate ranges from 0.2 to 1.3 km² in 2030 for the Climate Ambition and International Ambition scenarios. In 2040, the spatial requirement estimates range from 0.1-3.0 km² and in 2050 from 0.1-2.8 km². The slight decline in the maximum is explained by a minor decrease in maximum installed gasification capacity in the International Trade scenario.

The hydrogen gas turbines require relatively limited amounts of space: 0.1-0.5 km² in 2030, 0.4-2.0 km² in 2040 and 0.5-3.6 km² in 2050. While only CCGT's are installed in 2030, the share of GT's is larger in 2040 and 2050. Also here, refurbishing existing natural gas turbines or reusing the same locations may limit the amount of new space required for hydrogen turbines. The II3050 estimates that 0.5-0.9

km² is required for hydrogen gas turbines in 2050 [4], which aligns with the lower bound of our estimate.

Figure 34. Bandwidth estimates of spatial requirement for subsystems for hydrogen production and hydrogen turbines for electricity production. Low and high estimates are based on the low and high spatial footprint estimates per subsystem.

4.2 Spatial requirements in perspective

The spatial area requirement of the hydrogen system for 2050 in the Netherlands is contextualised by the illustration in Figure 35 comparing the results of this study with the spatial areas of other systems, such as the projected spatial requirement for onshore wind and solar farms towards 2050 from the II3050 scenarios. The estimated minimum hydrogen system spatial requirement of 99 km² and the maximum spatial requirement of 280 km² is shown in light purple, with the estimated minimum and maximum spatial area requirements of the hydrogen pipeline system of 88 km² and 125 km² respectively shown in darker purple. It can be seen that the hydrogen pipeline spatial requirement, consisting of new and repurposed HTL and RTL pipelines, significantly contributes to the total spatial area requirement of the analysed hydrogen system. This accounts for the majority of the space required in the minimum scenario and around half of the space required for the maximum scenario.

The spatial requirement of the hydrogen system is compared to the land area of Texel, the spatial area use of the gas and oil pipeline network in the Netherlands, and the projected spatial requirement for onshore wind and solar parks from the II3050 scenarios (orange blocks, Figure 35). The illustration shows that almost two times the land area of Texel of 160 km² [111] is potentially required for the maximum spatial requirement of the hydrogen system for 2050. The pipeline network for hazardous substances, namely gas and oil, occupied around 0.5% of the total land area of the Netherlands in 2012 [112], which amounts to about 170 km². This rises to 1% if safety contours for the network are included [112], amounting to 340 km² of space required. Without additional safety contours, the area

requirement of the main gas and oil pipeline network is about 30% larger than the estimated maximum space requirement for the hydrogen pipeline infrastructure.

Figure 35. Comparison of minimum and maximum hydrogen system space requirement (purple blocks) with other systems (orange blocks)

The I13050 scenarios estimated the space required for projected installed capacities for onshore wind, offshore wind, and solar parks for 2050 across the four scenarios. For onshore wind, a spatial requirement of 1,250-2,500 km² was estimated for projected installed capacities of 10-20 GW. The projected area for offshore wind amounts to 3,800-7,200 km² (not presented in Figure 35). For solar parks, a spatial requirement of 350-580 km² was estimated for projected installed capacities of 35-58 GW [4]. As with the hydrogen system, the area used for these renewable electricity production systems could also partially be used for other purposes. The projected spatial requirements for onshore wind and solar parks from the I13050 scenarios are both substantially larger than the estimated spatial requirement for the hydrogen system for 2050. The maximum area estimate of the analysed hydrogen system amounts to around 10% of the highest projected spatial use for onshore wind parks in 2050 from the I13050 study. It should be noted that a share of these systems will be needed to produce hydrogen locally from renewable electricity.

The spatial area requirement for the hydrogen system will be spread across the Netherlands and not aggregated in a single area as depicted in the above illustration. Production and import facilities may be concentrated in industrial clusters and ports, but other infrastructure components, like pipelines and refuelling stations, will be spread nationally. The spatial estimate includes components that can be repurposed from existing infrastructure, such as pipelines and storage facilities, which accounts for much of the space required. The amount of space that should be reserved for the hydrogen system

and in which region is difficult to project as large uncertainties exist and several subsystems can likely be repurposed from existing infrastructure. Given that the hydrogen system can partly reuse and repurpose existing subsystems and uses partly underground area, only a limited share of the 99-280 km² would likely require new, above-ground space.

4.3 Synthesis of the results, uncertainty, and recommendations

In this study, the spatial footprint of (a large part of) the future hydrogen system in the Netherlands is estimated. The total spatial area usage differs substantially between the different I13050 scenarios and based on optimistic or more conservative assumptions, ranging from 99 to 280 km² in 2050. The hydrogen pipeline network occupies most of the area requirements, 88-125 km² in 2050. If we subtract the area associated to the pipeline infrastructure, remaining subsystems require 11 to 155 km² in 2050. This bandwidth can, at first, be difficult to understand, but becomes more clear if the ranges are explained for the different subsystems and scenarios separately. Below we present the ranges of the different subsystems and shortly explain how we arrived at the optimistic and conservative estimates (Table 16).

Table 16. Summary of area ranges per subsystem and their contribution to the total space requirement in 2050.

	Spatial footprint factor ¹	Scenario capacity factor ¹	Optimistic estimate (km ²)	Conservative estimate (km ²)	Comments
Pipeline network	1	1.4	88	125	only varies per scenario
Underground storage	100	1.8	0.1	89	Range mainly caused due to difference between aboveground installations versus total licensed area of a depleted gas field
Refuelling stations	1.9	5.6	3	35	mainly varies per scenario
Electrolyzers (onshore)	4.4	2.5	1	11	Narrow range due to limited differences in spatial footprint range and scenarios, but assumes only large-scale installations
Electrolyzers (offshore)²	17	2.5	0.05	2	Range mainly caused due to difference in bandwidth of offshore installations with on the optimistic side several stacked floors of electrolysis equipment
Import terminals	6.8	4.4	2	21	Range determined by a combination of differences in spatial footprint and scenarios
SMR/ATR	4.2	5.2	0.1	2	Varies per scenario and due to differences in spatial footprint
Biomass gasification	8.5	2.3	0.8	4.5	Varies per scenario but mainly due to the broad range in spatial footprint
CCGT/GT	6.5	1.8	0.5	3.6	Varies mainly due to differences in spatial footprint
Total area use for a specific scenario (excl. pipeline network)			11	155	Optimistic = EUR scenario Conservative = INT scenario
Total area use for a specific scenario (incl. pipeline network)			99	280	Optimistic = EUR scenario Conservative = INT scenario

¹ The factor is determined by dividing the highest value within the range by the lowest value

² When offshore electrolysis is included in the scenarios

The total spatial use per scenario is determined by both the specific spatial footprint of each of the subsystems and their capacity, which is required for that specific scenario (and year). To illustrate the relative contributions of these two variables, we indicate the relative difference between the highest and lowest value in the bandwidths of these variables as a factor in Table 16. When most of the subsystems can be utilized according to their optimistic assumptions within a single scenario, the area usage can reach the most optimistic end of the range, i.e. the European Integration scenario with 11 km², while the conservative estimates combined result in the high end of our range, i.e. the International Trade scenario with 155 km² (both excl. pipeline network). This implies a significant difference in outcome, which is partly induced by alternative scenarios but also by the large bandwidths of spatial area use of the subsystems.

If we compare and validate our results with the spatial use estimates in both the I13050 and PEH studies, the assumptions and ranges do largely overlap. We should note that our ranges are generally broader and extended to more conservative values in comparison to the other studies. For several subsystems, this difference can be easily explained by a difference in assumptions that are made. For instance, for pipeline systems, the full area usage is included in our assessment while the I13050 study only reports the additional space used for the RTL network and considers the rest as repurposed existing pipeline corridors. For underground storage, we include the permitted area as a high end of the range while I13050 only considers the aboveground area required for underground hydrogen storage. The spatial assessment of the previous studies is by this work further extended, also to include other subsystems that are relevant for the entire hydrogen system. The validation of the assumptions for spatial requirements from the I13050 and PEH study and extended analysis of spatial requirements for key subsystems of the future hydrogen system are further substantiated by the detailed assessment reported in Chapter 3. The applied methodology can as well be extended to other subsystems or updated when new information is available.

4.3.1 Uncertainties in the analysis

The observed differences, both in the ranges that we find in our analysis and if we compare our results with the I13050 and PEH reports, can be largely explained by the uncertainties behind the analysis. First of all, uncertainties exist in the scenarios, which differ substantially in capacities and choice for different hydrogen subsystems. Secondly, the area use for existing and planned facilities differs substantially and results in a rather broad range in specific spatial area use for the different subsystems. Lastly, the designated space use is influenced by the definition of spatial area usage, e.g., which area is taken into account. By this we mean if, for instance, underground area, permitted area, and/or repurposed area is included in the analysis.

Uncertainties in scenarios – In the scenarios, supply and demand of hydrogen are matched but can largely differ in quantity and peak capacity. Besides this type of quantification, also the choice for specific applications can differ substantially. In the I13050 scenario, for instance, hydrogen is imported but no clear choice of method is provided. As we show that substantial differences in space use can exist between hydrogen import methods (e.g. through LH₂ or methanol), the choice for a specific carrier can have severe consequences on the total area requirements. Another example is represented by the required peak in energy use to heat buildings during winter and how hydrogen can contribute. Such a peak in capacity can, for instance, be solved by using hydrogen from underground storage facilities, but also by additional hydrogen import, or a combination of these options. The contributions of these options result in a certain capacity. This peak capacity is only used for a short period per year but nevertheless uses the required space the entire year. We should note that similar storage capacity is currently also available for natural gas to fulfil the same functionality.

Uncertainties in specific spatial footprints – The area requirement of a hydrogen subsystem is difficult to capture in a single value. Several aspects influence the plot size of a facility, such as the scale of a facility and the land price and availability in the region. Even for mature subsystems, substantial differences may exist in their plot sizes. The specific spatial footprint depends on the selected reference system or project and also on the boundaries selected for the measurement of the area. For CCGT's in the Netherlands, we observe a range in specific spatial area use of 4-26 ha/MW_e, which already indicates that a factor six difference is very common. We cover this level of uncertainty by using bandwidths of area requirement for a subsystem, preferably based on existing facilities and sometimes on designs and plans.

Uncertainties in definition of spatial area requirement – The designated spatial area use of a hydrogen subsystem is influenced by how this area is defined. If only the footprint of the installed equipment is considered, the total area usage is considerably smaller compared to a footprint estimate of an entire facility including auxiliary equipment, buildings, and surrounding area. The latter footprint can be even larger when also licensed, permitted, or underground area is incorporated in the spatial area assessment. The difference such a distinction can bring about is, for instance, resembled by the range described for underground hydrogen storage, which covers two orders of magnitude. The typical additional space that is necessary to ensure a certain level of safety falls out of the scope of our analysis. Nevertheless, in the described bandwidths of several of the subsystems, especially when based on existing facilities for which permits should have been provided, such a safety constraint is (at least partly) included.

Based on all these considerations, we believe that most uncertainty is covered by our high end of the described ranges and higher specific area requirements seem unlikely, unless, for instance, other risk and safety contours apply for specific locations. The spatial requirements can also be defined as solely new area that is necessary, excluding space that is already used for similar activities. Several hydrogen subsystems can make use of or replace already existing infrastructures, such as the natural gas network, underground storage facilities, refuelling stations, import terminals, and natural gas-fired power plants. The extent to which existing facilities will be repurposed is difficult to estimate and therefore only the total area requirements have been presented for the selected subsystems. In reality, a substantial share of the required spatial area may be space that is currently already been used for similar purposes and would not require new available land.

4.3.2 Recommendations for future research

Currently, a narrow quantification of the spatial area that is required to implement an entire Dutch hydrogen system proved challenging due to several uncertainties in the analysis. To arrive at a more accurate estimate, it will help to make a clear choice of the selected hydrogen subsystems and their capacities to fulfil a specific scenario. In that sense, it might be worthwhile to also explore scenarios in which the hydrogen subsystems that are implemented are clearly defined. Also for the type of area that is explored, for instance, total land area or only required new space, can be specified in more detail. We expect that even when several scenarios are explored, such a more detailed approach may substantially narrow down the bandwidth in area requirement. We should note that the relevance of such an analysis, however, may be limited as it is at the moment highly uncertain which subsystems will be implemented, in which form and at which capacity. Also the level of reusing or repurposing existing infrastructure and assets is difficult to quantify as it is likely that conventional applications also remain, at least partly, operational during the transition period.

Once more projects of hydrogen subsystems are being deployed, the accuracy of the specific spatial footprint of these subsystems can be improved. Periodic updates of our analysis may, thus, lead to new insights.

It may also be worthwhile to expand our analysis by including other systems that are impacted by the hydrogen system. This can provide insights in the influence of certain choices in hydrogen subsystems on the area requirements of these other systems, such as the electricity or fuel system. It may be possible that the spatial area use of a specific hydrogen subsystem, e.g. underground storage, results in substantially less land use for electricity grids or vice versa. This analysis can provide another piece of the puzzle and function as a starting point for more extensive assessments on the area requirements of the future energy system.

5. Conclusions

Our estimates for the spatial footprint of the hydrogen system cover a large range. In this report we have analysed the spatial footprint of the Dutch hydrogen system. In Chapter 2, the role of hydrogen in the II3050 scenarios is assessed. The assumptions behind and choices made in the four scenarios result in varying contribution of specific hydrogen subsystems. This represents the first source of uncertainty in assessing the area requirements of the hydrogen system. Next, as shown in Chapter 3, the spatial footprint for practically all of the subsystems also includes uncertainty. The specific spatial footprints per subsystem depends on the reference system or project and the boundaries selected for the measurement of the area. Part of these relatively large bandwidths originate from differences in the definition of spatial area requirement, i.e., for instance, is only equipment area included or the entire footprint of the permitted plot size. The compounded effect of the ranges in capacity and spatial footprint of each subsystem results in a large bandwidth in the total hydrogen system area requirement as well.

The total area requirements of the hydrogen system add up to 80-101 km² in 2030, 85-219 km² in 2040, and 99-280 km² in 2050. The International Trade scenario requires the most space for both the low and high estimates while the three other scenarios require less space and do not differ significantly. Based on the system footprint assessment and the aforementioned uncertainties, we share a number of general reflections below.

While the pipeline network takes up the largest amount of area requirements, much of the space is already in use for pipeline corridors and/or is suitable for multi-use. The pipeline network is responsible for a large part of the system spatial footprint with a contribution of 88–125 km² in 2050. But, importantly, substantial amounts of this space will exist out of existing natural gas pipelines that are repurposed for hydrogen. Similar to the existing natural gas grid, a significant part of the space required for corridors is also suitable for multi-use, for example as agricultural land.

The spatial footprint of underground hydrogen storage depends strongly on whether only the well and facilities are considered or the entire permitted plot size. Hydrogen storage also has a large total spatial footprint (0.1–89 km² in 2050), mainly when the entire area that is permitted and licensed is considered. On a large part of the plot, however, the space can still be used for other purposes. When considering only the well and the facilities, the spatial footprint shifts to the low end of the range and is significantly smaller.

Hydrogen refuelling stations have a large footprint (3–35 km² in 2050), but there are options to improve the footprint through more efficient use of space. In the scenarios with highest hydrogen use in transport, the estimated amount of hydrogen tank stations is larger than the approximately 4100 currently operational tank stations (for conventional fuels). The spatial footprint can be reduced by moving to larger capacities on the same plot and/or by integrating hydrogen tank facilities in existing refuelling stations.

There is a significant uncertainty about the footprint of hydrogen import terminals because of the difference between spatial footprints of the different hydrogen import methods/carriers. For hydrogen import terminals, the difference between types of terminals is significant. The spatial footprint ranges from relatively small for methanol storage to very large for liquid hydrogen. Also, within some of the import terminal types, the spread in footprints is large. For ammonia, for example, some existing and planned terminals achieve a significantly higher capacity in an area, reducing the specific footprint. In some instances, the capacity is also increased on the same plot, reducing the amount of space required per tonne of imported ammonia. The throughput relative to storage capacity also influences the required space for import terminals. Methanol reformers, ammonia crackers, and LOHC dehydrogenation units also add to the spatial footprint of hydrogen carrier import. We should note that both methanol and ammonia can be used as chemical feedstocks and/or fuels directly and do not necessarily have to be converted back to hydrogen. This would avoid the spatial area use of reconversion installations, which can also have a substantial impact on the total space requirements. All in all, the uncertainty of the form of hydrogen imports in the I13050 scenarios creates uncertainty in the estimate of the spatial footprint, which ranges from a total of 2 to 21 km² in 2050, that the hydrogen import terminals will have. It is therefore advisable to specify which hydrogen import terminals are envisioned to be part of the hydrogen system.

The terminals for peak import of hydrogen add a significant footprint, while their contribution to the imported volumes of hydrogen is small. Also here, specifying which import terminals are necessary will help improve the assessment of the spatial footprint. Alternatively, other solutions can possibly avoid the need for peak hydrogen supply and may limit the spatial implications for hydrogen import.

The spatial footprint of hydrogen production is relatively modest compared to the other subsystems, but it should be noted that renewable electricity supply is excluded from our scope. At an estimated maximum of 15 km², the spatial footprint of the hydrogen production subsystems is limited compared to the other subsystems. Of this, the onshore electrolyzers correspond to up to 11 km² for an installed capacity of 25 GW_e. Increasing the full load hours of the electrolyzers to more than 5500 operational hours per year can reduce the required amount of space for the same amount of hydrogen. Plant designs for offshore electrolysis show a significantly lower footprint, indicating that moving more electrolysis capacity offshore could potentially reduce the spatial footprint of electrolysis. Biomass gasification has a relatively large footprint, especially considering the relatively modest amount of hydrogen produced through this route. We should note here that the electrolyzers consume substantial amounts of electricity, and, as an example, if we assume that offshore wind requires roughly 1 km² for 10 MW_e capacity, a one-to-one (GW_e/GW_e) connection with an electrolyser plant requires an additional 100 km² per GW_e of installed electrolyser capacity. These area requirements of electricity supply have not been assessed.

For the subsystems that the I13050 or PEH studies have also made a spatial footprint estimate for, our estimates align well in terms of order of magnitude. The I13050 and PEH estimates tend to be on the lower side of the bandwidth of our estimates. The I13050 also made spatial footprint estimates for the HTL and RTL pipeline networks, electrolyzers, hydrogen storage, and hydrogen gas turbines. The PEH also includes a spatial estimate for gas import terminals, but it is not clear whether this refers to LNG or could also refer to hydrogen. The I13050 report indicates that the footprint of the pipeline network in 2050 is similar to the current natural gas network and the only additional space is required for the RTL network. While it seems clear that much of the existing pipeline network will be reused (or

the space would still be free to be used as farmland), the exact amount that can be repurposed is not yet certain. Therefore we indicate the total spatial area requirements of the future hydrogen HTL and RTL pipeline networks and conclude that these may need similar amounts of space as the current natural gas network is using. This implies that no (or not much) additional space will be necessary beyond the existing corridors.

The I13050 estimate for onshore electrolyser spatial footprint of 3-8 km² aligns well with our estimate of 1-11 km². We additionally include an estimate for offshore electrolysis of 0.05-2 km² if the I13050 scenarios contain offshore electrolysis capacity. In the I13050 area estimates, spatial use of offshore electrolysis is not specifically reported.

For hydrogen import terminals, hydrogen storage, and hydrogen gas turbines, the PEH and I13050 estimates lie at the lower end of the ranges of our estimates. For both hydrogen import terminals and hydrogen storage, the upper bounds of our ranges are significantly higher than the PEH and I13050 estimates, which clearly influences the total area requirements of the hydrogen system.

Despite the broad bandwidth of spatial use, the total area requirement of the analysed hydrogen system in the context of the I13050 scenarios is, in comparison to other systems, not excessive. Notably, our scope of the hydrogen system excludes energy supply, which will have a dramatic impact on the area requirements related to hydrogen production. Based on area requirements, thus, it should be possible to implement a hydrogen system within the Netherlands under the condition that energy supply for hydrogen production will not be a constraint. This study also indicates that for most subsystems, specific choices and designs may allow for a more efficient use of the space and thereby reduce the total area requirements, especially when considering new land area.

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Appendix – Conversion Factors

The table below outlines the conversion factors used to perform the analysis and provides additional information on some of the calculations.

Conversion Factor	Value	Comment
Unit conversion		
tonne of H ₂ to GJ	120	Lower heating value H ₂
tpa H ₂ to PJ H ₂	0.00012	Based on the lower heating value of H ₂
PJ H ₂ to MW H ₂	0.00243	1/3.6/8,760*1,000,000
Gas to LNG		
m ³ NG to m ³ LNG	0.00175	Gasunie Unit Converter
Density of carriers (tonnes/m³)		
m ³ to tonnes NH ₃	0.683	For storage of liquid ammonia at ~-33 degrees Celsius. A 90% capacity utilisation factor was also applied when not already included in the data available
m ³ to tonnes LH ₂	0.0709	For storage at ~-253 degrees Celsius
m ³ to tonnes methanol	0.794	For storage at ambient temperatures and pressures
Carrier to H₂		
NH ₃ to H ₂ (kg _{H2} /kg _{NH3})	0.15	Derived from the Fluor ammonia cracker study, where it was estimated that 3,000 tons of H ₂ can be produced per day from 20,000 tons of NH ₃ [72]
LOHC to H ₂ (kg _{H2} /m ³ _{LOHC})	47 (MCH) 64 (PDBT)	Based on [15]
Methanol to H ₂ (kg _{H2} /kg _{CH3OH})	0.189	Calculated based on steam reforming of methanol: CH ₃ OH + H ₂ O -> CO ₂ + 3H ₂ . Molar masses of methanol (32.042 g/mole) and H ₂ (2.016 g/mole): (2.016*3)/32.042 = 0.189
Throughput		
Annual throughput factor (tonnes tank capacity to tpa for the facility)	36.7	Based on OCI ammonia import terminal for estimating tonnes per annum throughput from tank capacity in tonnes. Factor is average of current and future OCI tonnes capacity (30,000 tonnes and 90,000 tonnes respectively) in relation to current and future throughput capacity (1,200,000 tpa and 3,000,000 tpa respectively) [59]

Appendix – Overview of hydrogen system and key subsystems

